

UNIVERSITÄT TRIER
FB II - COMPUTERLINGUISTIK UND DIGITAL HUMANITIES
PROFESSUR FÜR DIGITAL HUMANITIES

MASTERARBEIT
ZUM ERLANGEN DES GRADES EINES
MASTER OF SCIENCE (M.SC.)

« Seuls les petits corpus ont le secret
des petits corpus » –
Explorative, Automated Analysis and Presentation
of the Correspondence of French Writer Constance
de Salm (1767–1845) in a Semantic Web Approach

Sarah Rebecca Ondraszek

1. Gutachter:	Prof. Dr. Christof Schöch
2. Gutachterin:	Dr. Mareike König

Trier, den 04. September 2023

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Explorative, automatisierte Analyse und
Präsentation der Korrespondenz der französischen
Schriftstellerin Constance de Salm (1767–1845) in
einem Semantic Web-Ansatz

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Abstract

The significance of research data is steadily increasing. Their analysis and re-use enable new scientific insights. Alongside large-scale digitisation projects and the interest in big data, small and medium-sized research institutions have also launched digitisation and indexing projects. Just a few years ago, there were no standards for such projects. Data were often created in accordance with specific research questions and the wishes of researchers – and are therefore not available in a standardised form. Today, the necessary standards are being established by research data infrastructure initiatives such as NFDI. Questions such as “How can data – regardless of size – be standardised and thus saved from ending up in the data graveyard?”, “How can data be made accessible and opened up for new research questions?” are becoming common in the research community and affect researchers regardless of their discipline. This thesis aims to explore the potential of transforming an existing data basis into a standardised linked open data model using the Semantic Web, ontologies and knowledge graphs. In addition, a new exploratory search option for the correspondence in the form of an interactive knowledge graph visualisation intends to enable renewed access to the data. Drawing on the limitations of the resulting user interface and visualisation, the project also outlines potential future research and improvements.

Zusammenfassung

Die Bedeutung von Forschungsdaten nimmt stetig zu. Ihre Analyse und Weiterverwendung ermöglichen neue wissenschaftliche Erkenntnisse. Neben groß angelegten Digitalisierungsprojekten und dem Interesse an Big Data haben auch kleine und mittelgroße Forschungseinrichtungen Digitalisierungs- und Erschließungsprojekte durchgeführt. Noch vor wenigen Jahren gab es keine Standards für solche Projekte. Die Daten wurden oft nach spezifischen Forschungsfragen und Wünschen der Forscher erstellt – und liegen daher nicht in standardisierter Form vor. Heute schaffen Forschungsdateninfrastruktur-Initiativen wie NFDI die notwendigen Standards. Fragen wie “Wie können Daten – unabhängig von ihrer Größe – standardisiert und damit vor dem Datenfriedhof bewahrt werden?”, “Wie können Daten zugänglich gemacht und für neue Forschungsfragen erschlossen werden?” werden in der Forschungsgemeinschaft immer häufiger gestellt und betreffen Forschende unabhängig von ihrer Disziplin. In dieser Arbeit soll das Potenzial der Umwandlung einer bestehenden Datenbasis in ein standardisiertes, verknüpftes, offenes Datenmodell unter Verwendung des Semantic Web, von Ontologien und Wissensgraphen untersucht werden. Darüber hinaus soll eine neue explorative Suchmöglichkeit für die Korrespondenz in Form einer interaktiven Wissensgraph-Visualisierung einen neuen Zugang zu den Daten ermöglichen. Ausgehend von den Grenzen der resultierenden Benutzerschnittstelle und der Visualisierung skizziert das Projekt auch mögliche künftige Forschungsansätze und Verbesserungen.

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GitHub Repositories and Website

Website: <https://wissen-vernetzen.github.io/>

GitHub repository with first code and results (baseline ontology, first version of extended ontology with instances):

https://github.com/sarahondraszek/stage_IHA_cds/tree/main

GitHub repository with most recent code and results:

https://github.com/sarahondraszek/ma_thesis_cds_ondraszek_2023/tree/master

GitHub repository for the website:

<https://github.com/wissen-vernetzen/wissen-vernetzen.github.io/tree/master>

List of Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
ATR	Automatic Text Recognition
CdS	Constance de Salm
CSS	Cascading Style Sheets
CSV	Comma-separated Values
DFG	Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft
DH	Digital Humanities
DHIP	Deutsches Historisches Institut Paris
DSE	Digital Scholarly Edition
e.g.	exempli gratia
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
etc.	et cetera
FOAF	Friend of a Friend
GGG	Giant Global Graph
GND	Gemeinsame Normdatei
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HTML	HyperText Markup Language
HTR	Handwritten Text Recognition
IDE	Intelligent Development Environment
i.e.	id est
JS	JavaScript
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data
KG	Knowledge Graph
LOD	Linked Open Data
LPG	Labeled Property Graph
MWS	Max Weber Stiftung

NLP	Natural Language Processing
NFDI	Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur
OA	Open Access
OD	Open Data
OS	Open Science
OWL	Web Ontology Language
RDM	Research Data Management
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RDFS	Resource Description Framework Schema
REST	Representational State Transfer
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organization Systems
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
TEI	Text Encoding Initiative
UI	User Interface
URI	Universal Resource Identifier
URL	Uniform Resource Locators
UX	User Experience
VIAF	Virtual International Authority File
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

1 Introduction

“Open Humanities, Open Culture”: In 2023, two universities in Trier and Luxembourg co-hosted the largest conference on digital humanities (DH), the DHd2023. Under this motto that follows the tides of methodological and ethical development in the (digital) humanities, researchers were able to gain new impressions in the shared conversation space and present and discuss their current research projects. Not only does the title of the conference represent both institutes and their ongoing projects exceptionally well, it also emphasises the relevance and omnipresence of intellectual change in the humanities and puts a key value – openness of cultural artefacts – in the spotlight of this important conference. Open access (OA), open data (OD) and open science (OS) as values and publication practices have dominated the field for some time, especially in the area of digitisation (Putnigs, 2021, p. 31).¹

The conference motto “Open Humanities, Open Culture” is intended to make an essential aspect of the DH’s self-image visible and explicit. [...] Prof. Dr. Christof Schöch emphasizes that the conference theme is intended to stimulate a discussion about the special conditions of openness in the humanities, which are not primarily based on measurement or survey data, but on digital representations of cultural artifacts in the broadest sense (General Press Trier University, 2023).

The broader vision of terms like OS or OA also relate to research data management (RDM). Now, to speak of *data* at the round table of ‘classic’ humanists is still not quite common but is gradually moving into the consciousness of researchers (Sahle & Kronenwett, 2013, p. 76). Schöch (2013) states that, despite the constant growth of publicly available research data due to digitisation, some humanists would not classify their objects of interest as data. Above all, this shows the necessity of defining what (research) data are. But not only the general definition of research data or their management worry the scientific community: Next to words like ‘big data’ or ‘information explosion’, this – if researchers decide that the term ‘data’ does indeed apply to their objects of interest – also launches questions about size and impact of data collections. ‘Smart’ data, meaning data that have been somehow analysed, structured and contextualised, is usually small in volume. Its creation is time-consuming and labour-intensive (Schöch, 2013). Worries about research data extend beyond the realm of big data and also encompass small (smart) data. While much attention is given to managing and analysing big data, it is important not to overlook the significance of

¹For this thesis, I use Zotero 6.0.26 to store and manage literary references. The inline citations as well as the list of references follow the American Psychology Association Format (7th edition). I compose this thesis in Latex using Overleaf.

small data. They offer diverse and concentrated analytical possibilities and therefore complement large corpora by supporting specific content and structured models despite limited resources. Collecting small data and smartening them up can lead to “data infrastructures that make them more big data-like – that is, amenable to combination with big data and open to analysis using big data [...]” (Kitchin & Lauriault, 2015, pp. 463–464). Worries about RDM surpass the realm of big data; ensuring data quality and regulated standards for reusability are essential regardless of the data set size.

One factor influencing the wider interest in research data is that many researchers have had and continue to have the realisation that data-intensive research is – independent of size – a necessity in order to work with complex, large data collections and thus unveil hidden patterns. (Digital) data are recognised as a treasure (Putnings, 2021, pp. 16–21). So be it measurements or texts, the pressing question of whether something classifies as data and what consequences this has for research projects means that more and more people in the scientific community actually have to deal with the challenge of RDM. Additionally, as the amount of (digital) data produced by humanity is increasing every year, and as technology continues to progress, the question of how to manage all this data in a sustainable way is becoming more and more prevalent, especially in projects funded by public institutions (Forschungsgemeinschaft, 2020; Putnings, 2021). Researchers must consider that not all data are equal, and RDM in the humanities operates under a different paradigm than in other disciplines (Sahle & Kronenwett, 2013, pp. 83–84). In order to establish normative, discipline-oriented standards and guidelines that help researchers in Germany on their path of generating, analysing and storing data, national organisations like the Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI) and their domain-specific consortia build supporting pillars on which they can orient themselves.² This is particularly important because the different regulations on *Länder*-level in Germany can lead to great inconsistency (Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI) e.V., 2023b; Putnings, 2021). On international levels, the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) establishes a global leadership role for the European community in RDM and enables European researchers to reap all the benefits of data-driven research (Putnings, 2021, p. 32). Additionally, the FAIR principles (FAIR standing for findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) provide a baseline for working with research data that is already being used all over the world (Putnings, 2021, pp. 215–238; Boeckhout et al., 2018, pp. 931–932). However, openness of data also requires that data sets are modelled in a structured and comprehensible way, not only but especially with annotations and metadata (Putnings, 2021, pp. 12–15, 413–415).

²National Research Data Infrastructure.

These debates are encouraging the collective research community to think about the future of research data. The increasing importance of openness of research data, publications and processes in many fields does not only concern universities (Fischer et al., 2022, sections “Kulturdaten über die GND vernetzen”, “GAIA-X&Kultur” and “NFDI4Culture”) but the entire scientific landscape, including the general public. This also includes, for example, the Federal Office of Administration (Bundesministerium des Innern, für Bau und Heimat, 2017) or municipal libraries (Rother, 2016). Thus, national institutions like the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) develop their own guidelines for projects in the field of digitisation and RDM (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft, 2015). Other foundations like the Max Weber Stiftung (MWS) also instruct their internationally operating institutes and the researchers working there on the conception of suitable guidelines for dealing with research data and publications (Max Weber Stiftung, 2022). This should also serve to counteract the large amount of unstructured and hardly reusable data on the internet. By working out dedicated plans for labelling, preserving and storing research data, one’s own research is thus prevented from disappearing into the black hole of “Dark Data” (Putnings, 2021, p. 15) and is left behind as smart(ish) data. DH as a pioneering, heterogeneous discipline incorporate these questions and how researchers deal with computational innovation and the increasing amount of possibilities (Berry, 2014, p. 48), most importantly in context of interdisciplinary approaches and get-togethers – from digital libraries or natural language processing to computational literary studies or digital history (Fickers, 2022; Hiltmann, 2022). This is also accompanied by the desire to expand the arsenal of (data analysis) methods and the overall renegotiation of knowledge production in the humanities (Berry, 2014; Hayles, 2012).

However, the actual implementation of interlinked, open data is costly and requires long-term considerations and plans for RDM (Putnings, 2021, pp. 131, 537). Even with data collections already standardised to some extent, and a norm of open data policies (Paic, 2021, pp. 11–12), they often stay untraceable and unusable for follow-up research (Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI) e.V., 2023a). This points at the importance of uniform, standardised data models and exchange formats.

Formalised, standardised models help to harmonise data and make them both machine-readable and traceable. The principles of the GO FAIR organisation are also particularly important here. These lines of thinking align with the precepts behind linked open data (LOD) approaches (Berners-Lee, 2006). As part of Semantic Web considerations, LOD enable links between machine-readable data sets from a wide variety of sources (Ontotext, 2022a) and help generate FAIR data (Schmidt & Thiery, 2020, pp. 213–214). The Semantic Web is a term – and concept – invented and

influenced mainly by Tim Berners-Lee. It focuses on “the web of data”, which strives to create a highly interlinked network of (all) data on the internet (Berners-Lee, 2006). However, instead of using hypertext, information in the Semantic Web is encoded in the Resource Description Format (RDF). Driven forward by machine-interpretable metadata and extended content information on data on the web, “computers are able to make meaningful interpretations similar to the way humans process information [...]” (Ontotext, 2022b). Ultimately, this portrays the “idea of a navigable space of interconnected objects [...]” (Ontotext, 2022b). Meanwhile, ontologies (Rehbein, 2017) and graph technologies (Kuczera, 2017, 2019) also make up a notable and promising part of open data modelling. Ontologies are formal descriptions of knowledge in a specified domain, embodied by concepts or entities and the relationships they share (Ontotext, 2022a).

So, in relation to uprising discussions about linked data and the web as a wholly interlinked database, graph technologies in information science gain importance as they offer new ways of structuring data. This has naturally also become a topic of interest for DH, library science and the like. Other than in relational databases, hierarchical formats like eXtensible Markup Language (XML) or tabular formats like Comma-separated values (CSV), a shift towards graph-based approaches helps structuring data in entities (nodes) and relationships (edges) with rich and flexible modeling. Knowledge graphs in particular merge with the principles of LOD, especially the idea of interlinking the web. They offer the possibility to connect multiple data sources and therefore provide a more holistic view of data in the graph. The application of knowledge graphs and graphs generally as way to structure and store data has expanded across various domains, e.g. RDF, artificial intelligence and – of course – search engines (Ehrlinger & Wöß, 2016; Ontotext, 2023).

This Master’s thesis takes part in the shift towards LOD that is concerning the scientific community by considering a specific digitisation project with already digitised and partly standardised research (meta)data: The correspondence of Constance de Salm (1767–1845) is an epistolary data basis that currently includes around 11,000 digitised and indexed documents. All these are available on the project’s website³, as well as on Zenodo⁴. Letters are particularly interesting for research in the humanities and, of course, especially in history, as they function as texts in which ideas of the self are continuously constructed, negotiated, defended or reformulated (Depkat & Pyta, 2021, p. 8). Along with diaries, letters thus emphasise self-thematisation in the context of social (writing) conventions in the collectively shared space of the respective time (Depkat

³<https://constance-de-salm.de/>.

⁴<https://zenodo.org/record/5707822>.

& Pyta, 2021, pp. 8–9). On the basis of letters and entire correspondences, historical theses can be validated. Moreover, they offer new perspectives on the respective time frames and can inspire new research questions. Letter editions are therefore important source works for historical research (Baillot, 2020, pp. 390–393; Dumont, 2022, pp. 729–734; Mücke, 2001, p. 88).

Like in the case of Constance de Salm and her digitised correspondence, editing letters and making them accessible to the public has a long tradition and is subject to changes and innovations in technological possibilities. However, in this Master’s thesis, I will not extensively discuss the development of digital editions, which have become part of the standard toolbox of (digital) humanities and have evolved from being included in CD-ROMs accompanying a book to user interfaces. Nevertheless, the development and maintenance of digital (letter) editions play a role in the discussion of RDM (Stäcker, 2020, pp. 2–4; Sahle, 2013b). Some libraries even consider managing digital editions as part of their future responsibilities. This includes issues related to the encoding and representation of the text to be edited, as well as the long-term storage of reusable (meta)data.

In her Master’s thesis, Bögel (2013) presents the problems of isolated solutions and metadata tailored to project-specific requirements. Over the past few years, the development and establishment of format and metadata standards such as the Text Encoding Initiative (TEI) and controlled vocabularies have resolved some of these issues. Libraries, in cooperation with other project partners, can participate in the standardisation of digital letter editions and aid to ensure compatibility and convertibility of resulting research data. However, as mentioned at the beginning of this introduction, the challenge remains of how projects can publish their data in a long-term and FAIR manner (Bögel, 2013; Stäcker, 2020).

Furthermore, digital editions are not limited to text alone; they now present themselves as a conglomerate of text, markup, semantic annotation, metadata, and visual representation – digital editions become the interface (Bleier et al., 2018; Sahle, 2013b, pp. 157–281). In addition to more classic questions of edition science, other practices enter the stage. Next to edition standards, researchers now also have to think about user interface (UI) usability (Matera et al., 2006) and user experience (UX) (Hassenzahl & Tractinsky, 2006) paradigms and principles. The fact that information visualisation principles constitute a new focus is still relatively new territory. Thus, new competences – such as website or software design – join the repertoire of researchers working on a digital edition (Sahle, 2013b, pp. 159, 249–254). Of particular interest in this context is how effective new, different types of visualisation are in a digital edition because “[i]nterfaces define how research material is presented. They shape the view recipients

acquire from historical sources” (Bleier & Klug, 2018, p. 5).

The digitisation process thus influences the ‘how’: How do we handle letters? How do we work with them digitally, and how do research results become sustainable and visible?

Das mit digitalen Briefeditionen, -repositorien, -metadatenverzeichnissen und sonstigen -datenbanken zusammenhängende Verlinkungspotential beantwortet ein lange zuvor bereits identifiziertes Forschungsdesiderat der Briefforschung. Briefe sind dadurch charakterisiert, dass sie nicht für sich bestehen, sondern auf externes Material, Ereignisse oder Personen verweisen. Ihre dialogische Struktur bettet Briefe in einen weitergehenden Informationszusammenhang ein [The linking potential associated with digital letter editions, repositories, metadata directories, and other databases addresses a long-standing research need in letter research. Letters are characterised by their reference to external materials, events, or persons. Their dialogue structure embeds letters in a broader information context] (Baillot, 2020, p. 390).

Network structures appear to be inherent in correspondences, as letters, their senders, and recipients represent relational, networked knowledge (Strobel, 2021, p. 52) that can be newly accessed through computationally processable data. Yet, to illustrate such information beyond the traditional network analysis and enable semantic connectivity (Dörpinghaus, 2022), a new encoding is required, as the original form of XML/TEI is not suitable for this purpose (Ciotti & Tomasi, 2016). There are already initial approaches to move beyond editing digital editions solely in XML/TEI and instead utilise alternative formats to enhance semantics, commenting documents and facilitate linkage to linked data (Dumont, 2019).

[...] der TEI Standard hat, entgegen den Intentionen seiner Schöpfer, nicht zu einer Interoperabilität von Editionen, sondern vielmehr zu einer immer stärkeren Auffächerung des Markups geführt. Daraus resultiert der Bedarf an Lösungen zur Aggregation, Nachnutzung und Vernetzung von Editionen sowie auch zur Erschließung über eine maschinenlesbare Semantik, die über Linked Open Data (LOD), Normdaten und andere Metadaten jedweder Form Verknüpfungen herzustellen in der Lage ist [the TEI standard, contrary to the intentions of its creators, has not led to interoperability among editions but rather to an increasing proliferation of markup variations. As a result, there is a need for solutions that facilitate the aggregation, reuse, and interlinking of editions, as well as the incorporation of machine-readable semantics through linked open data (LOD), controlled vocabularies, and other forms of metadata, enabling the establishment of connections] (Wettlaufer, 2018).

In his paper, Kuczera (2022) proposes detaching TEI semantics from the hierarchical structure of XML and, instead, employing a knowledge graph to prepare the digital

scholarly edition (DSE) of Hildegard von Bingen’s *Liber epistolarum*. Given that contextualisation and network structure are inherent to letters, it is a logical conclusion to employ a data management structure that supports this characteristic. This entails not only the encoding of text but also metadata. Such an approach facilitates the presentation of letters in “semantic multidimensionality” (Kuczera, 2019). Contextual information and the linking of data sets enable new research questions, analyses, and visualisation possibilities in interdisciplinary approaches (Dörpinghaus, 2022, p. 15). An example of how networking for different correspondences can look like is offered by *correspSearch*, a virtual catalogue of digital editions of letters (Dumont, 2022).

In the context of these developments, this thesis focuses on the question of how LOD approaches and knowledge graphs can improve the reusability and (visual) presentation of research data from smaller digitisation projects. The project seeks to extend the reach of Constance de Salm and her extensive corpus of letters by adding new spheres to the data, and aims to exploit novel ways of linking, indexing, visualising and analysing the corpus using semantic web technologies. This involves the implementation of a reusable, standardised, semi-automatic workflow for transforming, enriching and presenting the letters and their metadata in an interactive knowledge graph on the web. By transforming a subset of the letters into plain text for text mining purposes, I illustrate their potential and show how small data analysis can help generate knowledge; adding these results to the knowledge graph acts as a gateway to reveal hidden patterns in the data.

“Seuls les petits corpus ont le secret des petits corpus”⁵ – this modified quote with a twist demonstrates a cornerstone of this project. The actual quote, “Les petites âmes ont seules le secret des petites âmes.”⁶ originates from Constance de Salm’s *Pensées*, in which she discusses the neglect of women’s education, the dominant attitudes of men and the major problems of society at the time, also processing her dissatisfaction with living in the Rhineland. She maligns small souls for a lack of sense for what matters, for their different insights and distance to what moves and motivates ‘elevated’ souls, leaving up for interpretation who exactly she considers a small or elevated soul (Salm, 1842). While this thesis is not about feminist approaches per se, and also does not discuss who might be such a small soul, the title has been changed to provoke thoughts about small data: from today’s perspective, are small corpora undesirable because of the development of big data and do their different kinds of insights not bring value? Are small corpora indeed small souls?

In setting up and implementing this project, I am also concerned with how the

⁵Only small corpora have the secret of small corpora.

⁶An approximate English traduction would be: Small souls alone have the secret of small souls.

relationship of researchers to the sources changes when LOD are used. The practical-technological part is intended as a proof of concept to show that explorative, multiplied access (via an interactive knowledge graph visualisation) can make a renewed accessibility to research data possible.

Part of this goal is the transformation of the current metadata model (currently available for download as an Excel file) into a LOD-compliant and semantically enriched knowledge graph. In addition to the metadata manually extracted by previous researchers, I add another layer of automatically extracted keywords and sentiments. I intend to explore (and later let users explore) the benefits of transforming a data basis into a standardised LOD approach, using the Semantic Web, RDF and ontologies. Additionally, I use automatic text recognition (ATR) to transcribe a subsection of the letters in order to be able to perform text mining tasks on them (which aid with semi-automatic enrichment).⁷ To wrap it all up, I publish the data on a self-implemented website that also displays the graph in visual form – an (interactive) network of nodes and edges about the correspondence. All content on the website, but especially the graph, serve as a new gateway to the correspondence of Constance de Salm and support or even stimulate the exploratory search within letters, keywords, and the like without prior knowledge or concrete search queries.

First milestones for the FAIRification of the correspondence of Constance de Salm (CdS) have already been laid at the Deutsches Historisches Institut Paris (DHIP, German Historical Institute Paris), who digitised the correspondence and published it online: this is the first cornerstone for this Master's thesis. The metadata contain names of people and places with Gemeinsame Normdatei (GND) or Virtual International Authority File (VIAF) identifiers. All research data can be downloaded from Zenodo without registration. Also, the correspondence has been added to *correspSearch* (König & Peyronnet-Dryden, 2019, see section Projekt/Constance de Salm, ihre Korrespondenz und die Projektphasen/Überarbeitung, Datenkuratierung und Fairification). In order to connect to the constantly evolving theory of RDM, it is now a matter of linking the CdS data and increasing their interoperability.

For that purpose, I elaborated a project pipeline that works in several, circularly cooperating rounds in which I work on the different sub-tasks toward the main goal. First, I analyse the latest update of the data in Excel format and evaluate the quality. Especially its features (formats, data types, particularities) and error proneness are of

⁷Often, researchers speak of 'OCRisation' in this context. Since handwritten text recognition (HTR) and optical character recognition (OCR) continue to melt and software for text recognition becomes a broader topic of interdisciplinary interest, the term ATR gains popularity. In context of a DARIAH-EU Campus research project concerning automated recognition of written text, we decided to use ATR instead of either HTR or OCR. Hence the introduction of this new, at first odd sounding neologism. The project's blog: <https://harmoniseatr.hypotheses.org/>.

interest. Furthermore, I create a suitable model for the representation in an ontology. Instead of using my own vocabulary, I use existing ones from the start, such as the Web Ontology Language (OWL) (Bechhofer et al., 2004), RDF Schema (RDFS) (Guha & Brickley, 2004) and Friend of a Friend (FOAF) (Brickley & Miller, 2004). Simultaneously, I enrich the data via reconciliation in OpenRefine (Metaweb Technologies, Inc., 2023) and add all data points to the ontology. The merged data then wraps up in RDF/XML and CSV format. In this round, the letters from the correspondence are still only available as digital images.

Secondly, I transform the RDF/XML data into a labelled property graph, so I can manage it within the graph database management system Neo4j. I subsequently test a few options of how to visualise the graph in an interactive browser dashboard and create a first web interface using a Bootstrap model for HTML and JavaScript. Moreover, in this step, I transcribe a subset of the letters using ATR and manual post-correction in the tool Transkribus Lite.⁸ The results are then available as plain text files.

During the third round, all transcribed texts run through two text mining algorithms for keyword extraction and sentiment analysis, so that I can then add the additional information to the graph.

The fourth and final round combines all the data generated during the first phases and ends with a final beta version of the website, which includes an interactive, searchable graph, ontology definitions, and more information about the project. I also let a group of students and researchers at the DHIP test the beta version in regards of its usability.

The pipeline largely corresponds to the structure of this Master's thesis. While this chapter serves as an introduction, providing an overview of the background and context of the work, as well as of the central research goal, the second chapter covers the theoretical background. There, I address relevant scientific references and explain important concepts and terms. Main focus lays on RDM, FAIR and open data, the Semantic Web, information visualisation and user experience, plus a short résumé of how text analysis works. In chapter three, I describe the data basis and previous project phases. I also highlight why Constance de Salm's correspondence in particular is suitable for this type of data model transformation and visualisation goals.

After that, chapter four consists of the main part and describes the applied methodology. It gives further information on the previously described workflow and the research results. Chapter five describes the process of designing, developing and testing the website. I provide a summary of the key developments, followed by a detailed description of all functionalities and design choices within the context of the entire workflow. Throughout the discussion, I validate the results, and provide possible im-

⁸I chose the free version of Transkribus for economic reasons.

Figure 1: Workflow – From Excel to Semantically Enriched Graph: The different rounds represent working phases during this thesis.

plications. The discussion considers both practical and theoretical implications of the proof of concept workflow and the new data model, as well as the website. Additionally, they emphasise the limitations of the application and the resulting user interface and thereby outline potential improvements. The last chapter concludes this thesis with a recap and outlook on future research.

2 Research Basis

This chapter shortly summarises the current state of research for RDM, LOD principles, and the Semantic Web and thereby lays groundwork for the other chapters – simultaneously introducing the necessary terminology and concepts – and pinpoints how edition science is evolving. It also covers key aspects of text mining and semantic annotation.

2.1 Research Data Management in the Humanities and Other Disciplines

The following subsections elaborate on the necessity of research data management concepts given the increasing amount of publicly available data in context of leitmotifs such as open data or the FAIR principles.

2.1.1 Basics of Data and Their Management

Figure 2: Growth of the Internet from 1999 to 2017: The figure shows the growth of the web, image taken from Zakon (2018).

Handling data, the ever ongoing technological change and staying on top of it all has been concerning scholars of the 21st century (and way before) for a while (Big Data Framework, 2022; Hayles, 2012). Recently, with further development around data management, both on national and international levels, and an increasing amount of available data from dif-

ferent disciplines and areas, avoiding the topic becomes all but impossible. Big data is a defining key term and seemingly a catalyst for such a tremendous change (Reichert, 2014, pp. 9–28). But also data deluge (Frederick, 2019) and information explosion (Barnett, 1964) are buzzwords in this context. Big data collections are characterised by high volume, velocity and variety and usually require specific methods for analysis (De Mauro et al., 2014). It is equally a term that embodies the new era of using digital technologies (Reichert, 2014, pp. 9–10), partly arising from “[t]he need to process these increasingly larger (and unstructured) data sets [...]” (Big Data Framework, 2022). Data deluge and information explosion also show metaphorically how the increasing amounts of data preoccupy and engage humanity.

In numbers, Figure 2 illustrates the rapid change of data availability via the growth of the web from 1999 to 2017. Figure 3 shows the amount of data on the

web in zettabytes and gives a forecast to how much it could increase until 2025. A wide range of this data is unstructured (around 80%) and mostly unused (only 0.5% in use by companies or the like), although they include high-value information (Deep Talk, 2021). Given such an enormous increase of data strengthens the need for concrete knowledge and information management plans. This concerns all aspects of computer-aided data creation.

Figure 3: Amount of Data Created, Consumed, and Stored From 2010 to 2020: increase of data on the internet, including a forecast to 2025; taken from Taylor (2022).

And with that, media technologies of data acquisition and processing move into the centre of knowledge production (Reichert, 2014, p. 11). Research data are gaining in importance; its analysis and use enable new scientific insights. This makes it all the more important to find management techniques that support reusable and comprehensible standards (Cox & Verbaan, 2018; Klump & Bertelmann, 2013). The quickly evolving architecture of data infrastructures shows “a new form of data in the guise of big data” but also challenges how to think about “traditional small data” that evolve through new types of management and structuring techniques (Kitchin & Lauriault, 2015, p. 473). The term small data does not necessarily refer to only the size of the data in a literal sense. While it concerns data sets of a smaller volume, the concept of small surpasses the volume of data; characteristics like being bespoke and often of high quality, fidelity, and robustness adjoin to the definition of what makes small data small (Kitchin & Lauriault, 2015, pp. 463–464, 466). So how to master all those data?

First, in terms of big data analysis, the unstructured and semi-structured data that stem from HTTP-based web traffic pose a challenge. Structured data have a specified structure and can therefore be processed by machines, i.d. data in relational databases. Semi-structured data appear structured to the human eye but are actually not fully machine-comprehensible, as can be seen in XML files. Unstructured data are data without machine-readable structure, for example plain text, audio, images,

or the like, so they require preprocessing steps to make sense of them (Nandakwang & Chongstitvatana, 2020, p. 20). Finding new approaches and storage solutions, as well as analysis techniques that are able to extract meaningful information from this type of data, is thus a main goal for data wranglers (Big Data Framework, 2022). Secondly, it is not only the classic type of big data that needs to be supervised in terms of (re-)usability. Next to velocity, volume or veracity, small data collections should not fall out of the scope of interest (Cox & Verbaan, 2018, pp. 27–30).

[...] [T]he small data landscape is changing through the development of data infrastructures. Small data gain value and utility when made accessible for reuse and are combined with other datasets. As a consequence, much effort is being directed at building such infrastructures and in trying to harmonize small data, with respect to data standards, formats, metadata, and documentation, to ensure their compatibility with systems, maximize discoverability, and facilitate the linking together of datasets. The pressure to harmonize, share and reuse small data will continue to grow as research funders seek to gain the maximum return on their investment through new knowledge and innovations (Kitchin & Lauriault, 2015, p. 473).

Generally, the overall quantity of digital research data has been growing significantly, as research communities have contributed in their generation “[...] [because] funding organizations [...] require that data generated through publicly-funded research be made openly available if legally and ethically possible” (Harwell et al., 2019, p. 2). It has reached a volume that makes it necessary to understand the distribution and curation of digital research data as an independent mission that must already be dealt with during the research process (Kliegl et al., 2022, p. 2). There are new demands on how researchers share their results. Since the relevance of data is constantly increasing in research as well as in administration and the economy, there is a requirement for interlinking for intelligent use in overarching fields of application (Ronzheimer, 2022).

Research data are thus data, big or small – and also part of the deluge. They can stem from applied sciences, for example when resulting from weather measurements or chemical experiments, as well as evaluations or (psychological) surveys; but also (qualitative) data from the humanities are considered to be part of this accumulation (Cox & Verbaan, 2018, pp. 22–26). For further examples, see Figure 4. Metadata, plain texts or images and their

- Results of experiments _____
- Measurements collected in the field _____
- Software programmes and their outputs _____
- Interview audio recordings and transcripts _____
- Focus group transcripts _____
- Questionnaire responses _____
- Government surveys _____
- Images _____
- Moving images _____
- Historical documents _____
- Physical objects _____
- Social media data: tweets _____
- Logs of web server traffic or another activity _____

Figure 4: Types of (Research) Data (Cox & Verbaan, 2018, p. 22).

future use need to be thought about when being examined throughout a project. It is inevitable to thereby integrate the life cycle of research data and its phases (see Figure 5) into the workflow of the project. However, the importance of these data outside of their own project has not been wholly acknowledged for a long time, or has been difficult to take into consideration (Klump & Bertelmann, 2013, p. 574).

Figure 5: Data Management and Research Life Cycle: taken from Ojanen et al. (2021).

Research data and theoretical concepts around them bring new *façons de faire* into how scientists and entire institutes value their data and how they carry out their projects. In the big picture of open access and open data approaches, research data cannot be omitted. This suggests that creating and publishing data under public licenses is part of a global turn in research infrastructures and represents core motives of the contemporary 21st-century re-

search community. As the Bundesministerium des Innern, für Bau und Heimat (Federal Ministry of the Interior, for Building and Home Affairs) states:

Wir leben in einer Welt des rasanten Wandels. Mit fortschreitender Digitalisierung in allen Lebensbereichen eröffnen Wissenschaft und Technologien neue Möglichkeiten zur Informationsgewinnung, -verbreitung und -nutzung [We live in a world of rapid change. As digitisation continues in all areas of life, science and technology are opening up new ways of acquiring, disseminating and using information] (Bundesministerium des Innern, für Bau und Heimat, 2017).

In Germany, associations like NFDI were formed in 2020 for this purpose and in order to put an end to the unmanageable and incomprehensible handling of data (Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI) e.V., 2023b). As can be taken from the previous quote, it is also of interest within the government to formulate policies concerning the (re-)use of data. Hurdles, such as copyright issues or organisational chaos, require agreements related to concrete practice and a mental shift in the scientific community towards openness with regard to the re-usability of data (Fournier, 2021, pp. 1–4). Already nine years ago, Kramer (2014) reported that the “transparent researcher” would take on an important role. In order to prevent that up to 90 percent of all research data disappear after completion of a project (Büttner et al., 2011a, p. 5), researchers are to disclose their research data. These considerations are part of the goals of the open data

movement, which I elaborate on in the following subsection. Central government funding agencies such as the DFG have also incorporated these ideas into their guidelines in 2015 and 2019 (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft, 2015, 2019). Although there are no national guidelines in this regard (yet), at least in Germany, thinking about research data management is a supra-disciplinary obligation, e.g. when requesting research funding. However, initiatives such as the NFDI are working on ways to create universal community-specific agreements (Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI) e.V., 2023b, pp. 2–3). All regulations are intended to be a meaningful aid to the implementation of good scientific practice and to promote research in a way that guarantees usability for both the present and future generations. Interoperability of research data through consistent application of the FAIR principles, as well as comprehensive knowledge, e.g. about data structures or metadata, are indispensable. Investments in appropriate infrastructures, technological resources, appropriate training of researchers and many other aspects are part of this (Fournier, 2021, pp. 2–3).

Das Potenzial für eine spätere Nachnutzung dieser Informationen soll erhalten und durch ein professionelles Informationsmanagement ausgebaut werden. Der breite Zugang zu Forschungsdaten, so wird erwartet, erlaubt eine deutliche Verbesserung und neue Perspektiven für das wissenschaftliche Arbeiten. Es wird die Aussicht eröffnet, auf der Grundlage bereits vorhandener Ergebnisse einfacher und schneller zu neuen Erkenntnissen zu gelangen. Diese Nachnutzbarkeit schließt vor allem auch die Möglichkeiten ein, Ergebnisse leicht interdisziplinär in Beziehung setzen zu können [The potential for subsequent use of this information is to be preserved and expanded through professional information management. Broad access to research data, it is expected, will allow a significant improvement and new perspectives for scientific work. It opens up the prospect of arriving at new findings more easily and quickly on the basis of existing results. This reusability also includes, above all, the possibilities of being able to easily relate results in an interdisciplinary way] (Büttner et al., 2011a, p. 6).

Research data management therefore portrays both a collection of methods and a global change of practice for researchers. At the methodological level, data management (research) is characterised by systematic planning and execution of corresponding data-related tasks; all this considering legal or ethical aspects (Putnings, 2021, pp. 297–299).

Research data management (RDM) is about creating, finding, organising, storing, sharing and preserving data within any research process (Cox & Verbaan, 2018, p. 4).

The data generated must retain its scientific significance at every step and remain accessible for evaluation. Local solutions must always be considered in the context of an overarching research data infrastructure. The central issue is therefore information management (Büttner et al., 2011b, p. 13). Thought-out data management plans, the description and storage of metadata and appropriate quality management ensure the reusability and findability of the data. It is also a question of sustainable storage and availability, quality assurance and legally compliant accessibility, as well as of citable publications (Neumann, 2021, pp. 399–400; Friedrich & Recker, 2021, pp. 413–416). These requirements are supported by principles from the LOD approaches, which I introduce below.

2.1.2 Open Science, FAIR and Linked Open Data

The requirements for data management seamlessly merge with the principles of OS and FAIR, supporting data usability, their discoverability and availability. OS summarises the means to make scientific research, especially scientific knowledge, data, and methods, more globally accessible. The main principles include, for example, openness, transparency, collaboration and participation (Cox & Verbaan, 2018, pp. 45–47; OCDE, 2015, p. 56). The main aim is to improve the efficiency, quality, and sustainability of scientific research, further solving societal challenges by strengthening the global dialogue between science and society, hence facilitating all access to scientific knowledge (OCDE, 2015, p. 10–14, 96; Paic, 2021, pp. 8–11).

FAIR data and the principles behind them make up an important part of the current development of research data management and have established a minimum global standard. Both the FAIR principles and LOD approaches are closely intertwined; however, they do not necessarily overlap entirely (Collins et al., 2018, p. 21).

The FAIR principles were published in 2016 (Wilkinson et al., 2016); since then, initiatives such as GO FAIR push the agenda of increasing their acceptance and working towards their broad application (Putnings, 2021, pp. 217–218). While the FAIR principles provide frameworks for research data, ensuring that – even in future cases – data can be findable, accessed with clear licenses, integrated with other data sets, and reused by humans as well as machines, they also represent a greater goal. Certainly, the application of FAIRness increases the value and impact of research data, as well as their discoverability and potential for re-use. (Collins et al., 2018). At the same time, the FAIR principles are about creating awareness of the importance of their application and supporting researchers in implementing them. Since this requires a high level of pedagogical qualification (e.g. because a structured, forced mental change cannot happen overnight) and expertise in the field of RDM, implementation also requires a

network of international and disciplinary projects for support. Next to GO FAIR, GO CHANGE, GO TRAIN, and GO BUILD are also part of that initiative. GO CHANGE mainly concerns the promotion of a global mental change, whereas GO BUILD is for training future FAIR researchers. GO BUILD treats the need to have interoperable research data infrastructures (Putnings, 2021, pp. 217–222). Moreover, this includes the FORCE2023 conference, at which OS was discussed in a global interdisciplinary context.⁹

LOD refers to a set of best practices that can be used when publishing and interlinking structured, standardised data on the web (Bizer et al., 2009, p. 88). They can be categorised as part of the Semantic Web and are essential to realise it (Berners-Lee, 2006; Pattuelli et al., 2015). Normally, web technologies such as RDF and SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language (SPARQL) serve to represent and query linked data. When using linked data, but especially LOD, researchers can break down “information silos” (Ontotext, 2022a) within different projects, formats, or the like.

Creating linked data happens in four steps, as described by Berners-Lee (2006): The first rule says that it is necessary to identify entities in a linked data model with URIs. The second rule specifies that people should use HTTP URIs. The third rule determines that information should be served on the web against a URI. That way, users can look up properties and classes of ontologies or data sets, and get supplementary information from the RDF, RDFS, and OWL ontologies. The fourth rule is to interlink the data to extern repositories to create “a serious, unbounded web in which one can find al [sic] kinds of things, just as on the hypertext web we have managed to build” (Berners-Lee, 2006). LOD principles are a special case of linked data as their application does not only feature the same characteristics but also supports publication under an open license. To see if proper linked data sets classify as LOD, Berners-Lee (2006) invented the ‘5-star linked open data’ chart.

Figure 6: 5-Star Scheme for Linked Open Data by Berners-Lee (2006).

This also means that in general, FAIR principles can be applied to LOD, helping to

⁹<https://force11.org/force2023/>.

ensure that the research data published apply to the principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability. This means that FAIR and LOD share the common goal of improving data accessibility and usability. Nevertheless, FAIR data principles also apply to data that are shared ‘only’ under restricted access.

The concepts of FAIR and Open data should not be conflated. FAIR does not necessarily imply Open; data can be FAIR and shared under restrictions. It is important to retain this distinction to support uptake across the commercial sector and within communities that create sensitive data. [...] To maximise the benefits of making FAIR data a reality, and in the context of Open Science initiatives, the FAIR principles should be implemented in combination with a policy requirement that research data should be Open by default - that is, Open unless there is a good reason for restricting access or reuse (Collins et al., 2018, p. 21).

These frameworks and principles portray the state-of-the-art disposition in scientific conversation (but also the public interest) to structure and make sense of digital information – and hence generate knowledge. As I already reflected upon in the previous section, the information explosion and data deluge enhance the pressure to find ways to do this. However, classification of information and knowledge extraction are not an invention of the 21st century.

Ordering of knowledge is as old an activity of the human mind as reflection is. One thinks here of the systems of Aristotele, Leibniz or Linnaeus [...]. Ordering systems are deeply embedded in philosophical systems and appear in all domains of human knowledge. We classify and order knowledge as we grow up in our individual ontogenesis, and we classify and order knowledge as mankind to enable orientation, navigation through growing masses of information. The ordering of knowledge is a precondition to allow for the abundance of new ideas by endless recombinations, alterations of marked cornerstones of human insights, next to flipping and breaking them and in this way pushing knowledge to a next level. In short, ordering knowledge is a prerequisite to linking knowledge (Scharnhorst & Smiraglia, 2021, p. 2).

LOD builds upon concepts of the Semantic Web by publishing data and linking them together. This way, a network of machine-readable linked data makes aggregation, analysis and use of information from different sources possible. These possibilities are of interest to DH, and therefore to digital editions, because they help to link research data, such as historical documents or the like, within the Semantic Web, making it part of a larger, machine-readable knowledge base (Wettlaufer, 2018, p. 2). This procedure helps “bridging the semantic gap” (Okoye, 2020, p. 42) within domain knowledge.

2.2 Semantic Web, RDF and Knowledge Graphs

In the following subsection, I explain the idea behind the Semantic Web and connect it to LOD and OS approaches. Moreover, the subsection summarises how to get from data to knowledge (management) and introduces focal points of knowledge graphs.

2.2.1 Basics of the Semantic Web and Ontologies

Semantic Web technologies – not a recent development but rapidly gaining in popularity – as an extension of the Web 3.0, strive to make information interlinked and both human- and machine-readable. Through enrichment of structured, semantic information, contents of documents (those can be letters, novels, copper engravings, sheets of music, etc.) become accessible for computers. The Web 3.0 describes the era of linked data; in previous versions, things on the internet consisted of static or mostly encapsulated content. Instead of using hyperlinks, the Semantic Web represents each “object [... as] a part of a huge distributed database on the Internet which can be processed by computers, and results can be presented in a variety of formats as required by users” (Nandakwang & Chongstitvatana, 2020, p. 21). Those objects share meaningful, well-defined relationships, which explains the term semantic.

Figure 7: The Semantic Web Stack.

Meaning can be expressed in RDF, because it allows documents to make assertions and encode connections in the form of triples (in *subject* \rightarrow *predicate* \rightarrow *object* structure). This goes beyond the bare description of data and towards the possibility to define knowledge. XML allows to represent such information in a semi-structured way. Key components of the Semantic Web are RDF and RDFS, as well as OWL and SPARQL (see Figure 7

for more components) (Nandakwang & Chongstitvatana, 2020, p. 21).¹⁰

In RDF, a document makes assertions that particular things (people, Web pages or whatever) have properties (such as “is a sister of,” “is the author of”) with certain values (another person, another Web page). This structure turns out to be a natural way to describe the vast majority of the data

¹⁰There are also other, modern solutions to the storage of linked data in Turtle files or N-Triples. A more detailed description of alternative formats to RDF/XML can be found in this article: <https://medium.com/wallscope/understanding-linked-data-formats-rdf-xml-vs-turtle-vs-n-triples-eb931dbe9827>.

processed by machines. Subject and object are each identified by a Universal Resource Identifier (URI), just as used in a link on a Web page. (URLs, Uniform Resource Locators, are the most common type of URI.) The verbs are also identified by URIs, which enables anyone to define a new concept, a new verb, just by defining a URI for it somewhere on the Web (Berners-Lee et al., 2001, see Section Knowledge Representation).

This indicates that RDF-triples form *graph* structures of information and, since entities and relationships are encoded in URIs (they are *resources*), it is ensured “that concepts are not just words in a document but are tied to a unique definition that everyone can find on the Web” (Berners-Lee et al., 2001, see Section Knowledge Representation).

To interlink multiple databases that use different identifiers for similar things, such conceptual information must be somehow encoded in a compatible way. Ontologies provide a framework for taxonomies; they capture concepts, relationships, and properties and their semantics of the domain. Therefore, knowledge can be explicitly and formally described. So, ontologies provide the common vocabulary and shared understanding needed for data interoperability and integration in the Semantic Web. Concepts in an ontology describe classes and types of things, outlining their characteristics. Relationships describe connections between concepts in an ontology. This aids to structure data on the Semantic Web so that data can be linked and queried across different sources (Berners-Lee et al., 2001, see Section Ontologies).

LOD and the Semantic Web are aligned concepts that enhance the accessibility and interoperability of data on the web. They combine interconnectivity, ontologies, RDF data models and semantic technologies to facilitate the publication and reusability of documents and their (meta)data. This way, structured data build an interconnected and machine-readable web. The development of frameworks for the Semantic Web and, accordingly, the steps towards a Giant Global Graph (GGG)¹¹, show how “[t]he Web has begun to develop from a medium for publishing and linking documents into a medium for publishing and linking both documents and data” (Bizer, 2009, p. 92). The World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) founded a leading project in 2007 that treats publishing linked (open) data online: the Linking Open Data project, which nowadays wears the label Linked Open Data Cloud.¹² The ongoing aim is to enable creating the GGG by “identifying existing data sets that are available under open licenses, converting them to RDF according to the Linked Data principles, and publishing them on the Web” (Bizer, 2009, p. 88). Publishing linked data connects to the Semantic Web and adheres to

¹¹Wayback Machine entry of the blog post in the forum *Nodalities*, written by Paul Miller: https://web.archive.org/web/20071201102224/http://blogs.talis.com/nodalities/2007/11/who_is_afraid_of_the_ggg.php.

¹²<https://lod-cloud.net/>.

the principles I explained in the previous paragraphs. It therefore enables data to be shared and discovered in interlinked resources, which contributes to the formation of a “web of data” (Bizer et al., 2009, pp. 6–10). Accordingly, the LOD cloud became a lighthouse for other projects in the sea of linked data. Since its foundation in 2007, the number of publicly available data sets increased considerably (from 2007 to 2017, the quantity increased by factor 100) and nowadays includes established repositories like DBpedia and Wikidata (Candela et al., 2022, p. 22; Zloch et al., 2019, p. 1).¹³

Status of the LOD Cloud in 2007 (image taken from Wikidata, permission given in an CC BY-SA 3.0 license by Andrejs Abele, John P. McCrae, Paul Buitelaar, Anja Jentzsch and Richard Cyganiak via LOD Cloud).

Status of the LOD Cloud in 2017 (image taken from Wikidata, permission given in an CC BY-SA 3.0 license via LOD Cloud).

Figure 8: Evolution of the Linked Open Data Cloud from 2007 to 2017.

2.2.2 From Data to Knowledge Management and Graphs

As I already explained in subsection 2.1.1, the increasing volume and complexity of data demands advanced (R)DM methods. Following the lead of LOD projects, adopting FAIR principles and utilising semantic technologies already helps to make data more accessible, interconnected, and meaningful. Enter another state-of-the-art system, the knowledge graph (KG), which offers possibilities to store, manage and smarten up data.

The core of a KG is a model that defines what kind of knowledge it contains. This is a collection of interlinked, well-defined definitions of concepts, entities, their relationships or the like that cover a specific domain. KGs contextualise data through

¹³Wikidata (https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Main_Page) is an open knowledge repository including structured data from Wikipedia and Co. DBpedia (<https://www.dbpedia.org/about/>) also extracts structured content from Wikimedia projects like Wikipedia and collects it in an open knowledge graph.

Figure 9: What Makes a Knowledge Graph a Knowledge Graph? Visualisation taken from Ontotext (2023).

connectivity and semantic enrichment. They thus tie in directly with the developments of the Semantic Web and LOD and offer mighty solutions in relation to organisation and representation of both structured and unstructured data. Combined technologies like RDF and ontologies help to create rich and flexible models for representing complex knowledge that can be queried and connected with external resources, through which additional knowledge about the data can be inferred (Kejriwal et al., 2019, pp. 1–2; Debattista et al., 2018; Ontotext, 2023).

Long before the Google Knowledge Graph, or even the popularity of the now ubiquitous phrase ‘knowledge graph’, in the Semantic Web, we have a history of being consistently focused on combining knowledge and data at scale by using graphs and semantics as a means to integrate, unify, interpret, augment and query data from diverse and multiple sources at web scale. [...] Arguably, the LOD initiative was one of the earliest instances, using Web protocols and publishing standards, to publish what we now call knowledge graphs as ‘linked data’ (Kejriwal et al., 2019, p. 1).

Google introduced its semantically enhanced knowledge base in 2012, following the motto “Introducing the Knowledge Graph: things, not strings”¹⁴, ensuing a boom of interest in the term KG and what is behind it. Ehrlinger and Wöß (2016) discuss whether a definition of KGs is possible, since so many different interpretations of its meaning emerged since 2012. They also strive to differentiate between knowledge bases and KGs, describing that while knowledge bases (they also put ontologies under this umbrella term) model domain-specific semantic knowledge in a smaller scale (so, not a wholly interconnected Semantic Web), KGs provide the possibility to do machine

¹⁴Google blog post from 2012, written by Amit Singhal: <https://blog.google/products/search/introducing-knowledge-graph-things-not/>.

reasoning in order to gain new insights. They are often also supposed to be large in size (Ehrlinger & Wöß, 2016, pp. 3–4). As a finite definition for this Master’s thesis, I follow Haslhofer et al. (2018):

Knowledge graphs represent concepts (e.g., people, places, events) and their semantic relationships. As a data structure, they underpin a digital information system, support users in resource discovery and retrieval, and are useful for navigation and visualization purposes. Within the libraries and humanities domain, knowledge graphs are typically rooted in knowledge organization systems, which have a century-old tradition and have undergone their digital transformation with the advent of the Web and Linked Data. Being exposed to the Web, metadata and concept definitions are now forming an interconnected and decentralized global knowledge network that can be curated and enriched by community-driven editorial processes (Haslhofer et al., 2018, p. 1).

Now, it becomes evident that KGs for data management surpass representation aspects. Storing and maintaining data that way aids with creation of contextualised knowledge by 1) organising structured information in a graph-like structure, encapsulating relationships and connections between entities and 2) offering the possibility to query data over multiple resources. This means that extraction of meaningful insights is possible.

Figure 10: The Data, Information, Knowledge and Wisdom (DIKW) Model: The figure illustrates how different data analysis steps generate knowledge and wisdom; image taken from Rao (2018).

Ideally, KGs implement data governance practices like those given by LOD and/or FAIR principles and use documented ontologies, enabling efficient sharing and reusability. Researchers go from (raw) data to knowledge in this way, as structured organisation leads to information and then, through associated context, reasoning, inference, and analysis, to knowledge (Rao, 2018). Figure 10 shows the way from data to knowledge (and wisdom), also picturing the process layers. Overall, KGs in RDM encourage people to think about the value of data and their

future use by promoting data-driven research and laying roots for the creators themselves and others to acquire a richer insight into complex phenomena by generating knowledge from data.

Cross-domain knowledge graphs, as they are emerging in the libraries and digital humanities domain, open a whole new spectrum of research opportunities. They can, for instance, inform the design of quantitative analytics tasks being applied on possibly large-scale document corpora. Taking into account the numerous digitization efforts in the library and humanities domain, knowledge graphs can be vehicles for connecting and exchanging findings as well as factual knowledge gained by applying those task on copora [sic!]. This can also stimulate the development of novel, mixed methods research methodologies (Haslhofer et al., 2018, p. 2).

2.3 Semantic Web in Digital Editions of Correspondences and Historical Research

The previous sections illustrate the developments in terms of RDM, Semantic Web and LOD applications. Wettlaufer (2018) notes in his article that the concept of Semantic Web is hardly mentioned in German standard works of digital editing science.¹⁵ However, the extraction of knowledge from raw data, and thus from (historical) documents, is a crucial part of edition processes.

Creating a digital edition means first creating an adequate markup model. The encoding scheme must respond both to the nature of the primary source and to the computational objectives; it's necessary to consider, on the one hand, which text features we want to focus on, and on the other, what kind of digital representation we want to give them. This means reasoning about data, with the aim of creating suitable information and extracting knowledge from the source (Tomasi, 2012, p. 201).

Traditionally, when creating a digital edition of letters, the full texts (if available) receive a markup in XML and are made searchable using keywords and (manual) annotations in registers (Strobel, 2014). In addition to aims regarding edition guidelines, editorial statements, visualisation and web presence, there are those regarding research data and their management. The question of semantic annotation in DSEs arises on two levels: on the one hand, there are linking aspects, and on the other, markup aspects. Between the established XML standards, in which TEI in particular occupies the position of excellence, and the semantic front, the question arises as to a solution that makes it possible to describe an edition as a whole and to link it to other resources. This includes, for example, other DSEs (Ciotti & Tomasi, 2016; Wettlaufer, 2018).

Formal semantics and descriptive ontologies for markup have been theorised and developed since the early 2000s (Ciotti & Tomasi, 2016; Kuczera, 2019) and are now

¹⁵For example, he mentions that Patrick Sahle's 2013a digital edition science trilogy does not cover the topic.

already used in edition projects. OA digital (letter) editions distinguish themselves through the networking of knowledge bases; to connect editorial data to normative data repositories like the GND or VIAF has become a minimal standard for most projects. Editions use structured and standardised metadata to increase their reusability (Strobel, 2014, pp. 151–152). Examples for such projects are Tomasi (2012), Beretta (2021), Wettlaufer et al. (2015), Schmidt and Thiery (2020) or Kuczera (2019), those also use semantic technologies for both markup and metadata description in their projects. Transforming a ‘simple’ TEI standard into a fully LOD-compliant Semantic Web framework is yet a costly endeavour, especially when projects are well-advanced. Although some projects oppose the information silos of DSEs (e.g. *correspSearch* by Dumont (2022)), the standards of individual projects continue to diffuse strongly (Ciotti & Tomasi, 2016; Meyer, 2019; Wettlaufer, 2018).

Digital letter editions are qualified for data management and representation in knowledge graphs based on their inherent relational structure (Strobel, 2021, pp. 30–41, 60). Letters and entire correspondences have to be understood as part of a bigger correspondence network (Dumont, 2019, p. 8). KGs for DSEs are henceforth included in current considerations as data management tools: They make it possible to link digital editions within the Semantic Web and thus make them part of a larger, machine-readable knowledge base, which in the future might enable completely new forms of contextualisation of knowledge (Wettlaufer, 2018, p. 2). Correspondences rest upon networks between letters, individuals, places, topics, and similar (Strobel, 2021, p. 52). Since Semantic Web technologies and KGs distinguish themselves in the area of interconnectivity, correspondences’ inherent graph-like structures can be captured in nodes and edges. Graph-based representations allow for the explicit modelling of the complex web of connections within the correspondence, enabling a more comprehensive understanding of the relationships between letters, authors, recipients, dates, and other relevant entities (Dumont, 2022, pp. 734–744; Dumont, 2019, pp. 8, 17; Baillot, 2020, pp. 390–392).

Furthermore, knowledge graphs help to provide flexibility, especially for contextualisation of various data within a broader frame. Connecting entities, concepts and relationships contained in the correspondence with other related entities and concepts from external records or resources, such as historical data, biographical information or geographical data, adds contextual information to the edition. Researchers may navigate through such connections, explore related materials and gain deeper insights into the correspondence and its meaning in the historical and cultural context (Strobel, 2014, p. 152; Dumont, 2019, p. 8).

The aim of the creation of an external knowledge is double: on the one hand it guarantees interoperability of the edition (it still is open to any dialogue with other repositories and systems) [...]; on the other hand it gives scholars a useful tool [...] and a method [...] that can be used and reused in a number of different contexts and situations (Tomasi, 2012, p. 217).

Wettlaufer et al. (2015) argues that most editions are already web residents and meet most of the 5-star LOD paradigm. So, theoretically, they would be ready to enter the world of linked knowledge – however, they still have to conquer the last two levels for opening a digital edition to the Semantic Web. This includes the conversion to open web standards, namely RDF and SPARQL, for identification of information in the edition, as well as links to external resources.

Knowledge bases, ontologies and semantic technologies also make it possible to combine different levels of interpretation in combination with the object being examined and thereby meet the correspondences' contextualisation requirements. The semantic, scholarly commenting and enrichment of the edition allows frames, i.e. knowledge frames that reflect concepts of collectively understood schemes. Incorporating ontologies and standardised, open vocabularies, adds semantic meaning to the correspondence. Domain-specific elements can be assigned to a frame and even modelled – this means that differences between historical concepts that are unknown to researchers or users today can be bridged. This way, specific parts – supplemented with links to external resources and/or interpretations – gain utility within the edition (Strobel, 2014, pp. 157–158; Dumont, 2019, pp. 5–6).

Similar thoughts apply to the field of digital history. Because researchers who work with historical documents always have to consider context dependent approaches to the object, various interpretations of such are possible. This can be portrayed using ontologies and an annotated knowledge base. If historical research data are published under FAIR and open standards, the general, public understanding of history and the past enhances (Meroño-Peñuela et al., 2015, p. 540). By connecting them to the web, it becomes possible to promote semantic interoperability and collective, collaborative historical narratives. Through automatic text processing and text mining, as well as linking the data not only with authority data such as the GND but with other RDF knowledge bases, the data are opened up for other researchers, but also for machines and retrieval systems (Meroño-Peñuela et al., 2015, pp. 553–555, 560–561).

Despite all the positive aspects, the Semantic Web poses problems for historical research, too: In particular, the modelling of time, change or language must be carried out with particular attention. Among other things, this involves unclear statements about data that have not yet been modelled, such as data from historical events or personal data. There are already vocabularies and ontologies for such statements, but

they are not yet complete and often not recognised in the entire research field. Different interpretations of the same resources or incomplete knowledge bases also make reasoning or interference more difficult (Meroño-Peñuela et al., 2015, pp. 556–559).

Since digital (letter) editions nowadays function as a decentralised instrument (Strobel, 2014, p. 152) – for example do they represent a research platform, presentation surface and entry point in one – users dealing with the correspondence in isolation became a rare case. Additionally, editions undergo a change of perspective: Transcriptions fade from the main spotlight while harmonised and standardised metadata enter the stage.

Fluchtpunkt der digitalen (Brief-)Edition ist [...] nicht ein Lesetext, nicht eine Transkription – sondern die Summe der vielfältig durchsuchbaren und weitestgehend normierten Metadaten [The central point of the digital (letter) edition is [...] not a reading text, not a transcription – but the sum of the variously searchable and largely standardised metadata] (Strobel, 2014, p. 153).

It comes to the fore that dealing with available data drives forward a new reading and research process that transcends the presentation of manuscripts, their transcripts and overall, the capsuled contents of digital editions themselves (Strobel, 2014, pp. 152–153). DSEs thus require (external) linking; KGs promote such comprehensive and interdisciplinary exploration. They simplify (scientific) analyses due to interlinking of diverse data sets from resources that cover historic, geographic, sociological, or similar input. DSEs become cross-disciplinary knowledge ecosystems. So, they portray interactive meeting and discussion, as well as collaborative working spaces – they turn into virtual salons. This also helps enhancing editions with external ideas and insights (Strobel, 2014, p. 152; Wettlaufer, 2018, pp. 13–14; Dumont, 2022, pp. 729–734, 744–747; Dumont, 2019, pp. 19–20).

KGs can help implementing LOD and FAIR principles; publishing the data under these circumstances helps with future discoverability, access, and reusability. This hence applies to current requirements concerning RDM and good practice of (open) science (Dörpinghaus, 2022, pp. 11–13). The application of graph-like structures to DSEs (of correspondences) facilitates flexible extension of the knowledge base, which adheres to the paradigm of the incompleteness of DSEs (“Unabschließbarkeit”) (Strobel, 2014, p. 152; Wettlaufer, 2018). Last but not least, RDF can also aid with versioning different steps of a project, especially changes in the data basis (Bürgermeister, 2020).

2.4 (Graph) Visualisation and UX-Design for Digital Scholarly Editions of Letters

As I already stated in the preceding section, DSEs (of correspondences) have surpassed their function as traditional linear editions and nowadays take form as graphical user interfaces (GUIs). In current implementations of DSEs, the starting points are often metadata indexes that give users clues as what to search in regards of the documents' topics, authors or the like (Stäcker, 2020, pp. 7–9; Strobel, 2014, p. 153; Baillot, 2018, pp. 8–9).

Next to implementations in RDM or markup of texts, that is also the reason why digital editions require an interdisciplinary set of skills to make their new form as GUIs usable and, what often is forgotten, aesthetically pleasing to users (Stäcker, 2020, p. 6). This involves UI and UX design, as well as usability. UI design is the process of designing the final interface of a software or website product. Its qualitative attribute, usability, covers aspects such as learnability or efficiency of the software. UX is concerned with the user's interaction and experience with such a product - including design aspects of adapting the interface to the user's needs and creating an enjoyable product (Hassenzahl & Tractinsky, 2006; Kurosu, 2020; Norman & Nielsen, n.d.).

Visualising the facsimiles, their markup and plain text versions has definitely been a main concern of the past few years in edition science (Dumont, 2019, pp. 19–20). However, with growing numbers of available metadata, UI/UX design and information visualisation also has taken a key role (Nazemi, 2016, pp. 1–4; Stäcker, 2020, p. 3–7; Ciuccarelli & Elli, 2019). Since “[o]ur brain is a pattern-seeking machine, made especially to process visual signals” (Ciuccarelli & Elli, 2019), visual cues on interfaces help users to process the large(r) amounts of data from the edition more efficiently.

[...] [V]isualizations are rapidly becoming ubiquitous in the humanities, not because they are ‘trendy’, beguiling, or merely decorative, but because they are powerful, effective, and efficient (Ciuccarelli & Elli, 2019).

When all correspondence metadata and contextualised information are given in graph-like form, another level of information processing suggests itself (Baillot, 2018, p. 3): Is a graph just a machine-readable, mathematical way to structure data? How can structured metadata help users discover the digital edition?

Despite the fact that graphs¹⁶ – as abstract, mathematical data structures – are not inherently visual, their visual representation can be interpreted by humans. A

¹⁶The term graph and network are often used interchangeably in literature; the term graph is more important for this thesis, however, for a short sidenote about network analysis, I will also use both terms synonymously.

prominent example are correspondence networks in which relationships between authors and recipients of letters can be displayed (Baillot, 2018, pp. 1–3). The histoGraph that was implemented by Novak et al. (2014) is an interactive tool built for “explorative visualisation and collaborative investigation of historical social networks from multimedia collections” (Novak et al., 2014, p. 241), exemplary shows how this works in user interfaces. Visual elements such as nodes, edges, specified colours, shapes, and layouts portray structure and connection within the graph. This simplifies how users might comprehend the relationships and patterns in the data. Furthermore, through the visual preparation of knowledge graphs in particular, complex structural features, contextualisations and patterns can be revealed, even by non-expert users (Venturini et al., 2021, pp. 1–2).

L’analyse de réseau ne transforme pas nos objets d’étude, elle transforme le regard que le chercheur porte sur ceux-ci. Organisée en réseau, l’information devient relationnelle. Elle rend possible en puissance la création d’une nouvelle connaissance [...] [Network analysis does not transform our objects of study; it transforms the way the researcher looks at them. Organised as a network, information becomes relational. It potentially makes it possible to create new knowledge [...]] (Grandjean, 2014).

In order to make it easier for users who have not yet had contact with the Semantic Web and knowledge graphs to get started with the data, it makes sense to work with representation tools. Today, most known methods of creating semantics visualisations are based on visualising the basic ontologies or hierarchical, taxonomic information (Nazemi et al., 2015, pp. 78–80). As can be seen, for example, in Protégé’s OntoGraf (Figure 11) (Musen, 2015), visualisations can already be output throughout the development process. However, there is a lack of tools to support users in later phases of data exploration, especially with larger amounts of linked data. This is where the interactive, adaptive information visualisation of semantic data comes into play. They give users means to explore the data bases intuitively, whereby they can dive deeper into their worlds, understand their context and think of more questions to ask. An interactive experience with a visual object they can manipulate by zooming in and out or navigating through, facilitates such insights into structure and context of the data, reducing the learning curve associated with traditional textual interfaces (pp. 76, 81–82 Cambridge Intelligence, 2022, pp. 4, 14–15).

While information visualisation focuses primarily on strengthening cognitive processes through visual representation, adaptive information visualisation in combination with visual analytics serve to adapt to individual research interests. For example, users can formulate search queries to the visualisation of the semantic graph, which

Figure 11: Visualisation of a Simple Correspondence Ontology in Protégé: This visualisation shows classes and their relationships that I created for the Constance de Salm ontology.

opens up new ways of extracting patterns (Nazemi, 2016, pp. 1–2, 123–124). Since specific domain knowledge is necessary to think up such concrete queries for an edition – or for a data set in general – it makes sense to support users in thinking them up. Implementations need to focus on information visualisation, which enhances exploration, analysis, decision making, or explanation, and information seeking (Fähle & Sack, 2023, p. 43; Nazemi et al., 2021, p. 479; Nazemi, 2016, pp. 92–93). Nazemi (2016) calls this exploratory search in semantics visualisation, in which “semantics is defined as data with meaningful relations of at least two information or data entities” (Nazemi, 2016, p. 94) and exploratory search is a browsing behaviour that focuses the acquisition of new knowledge (White & Roth, 2009, pp. 9–23), including activities like “Lookup, Learn, and Investigate” (Nazemi, 2016, p. 94).

Semantics visualization supports actively the information seeking process with the underlying steps of Lookup, Learning, and Investigate to amplify cognition in the search process. The main goal is to provide user-centered interactive graphical representations for solving visual tasks with semantics and supports in best case the entire search process. Therewith semantics visualization bridges the three dimensional gap between users, tasks and data (Nazemi, 2016, p. 94).

Giving users hints and tools as a direct entry point to the edition is reasonable

Figure 12: SemaGraph Layout: Nazemi’s 2016 tool SemaVis supports users in linked data exploration using a visual interface. Image taken from p. 311.

because often, research in digital editions is focused on search and exploratory content (Düring et al., 2021, p. 1). Graph visualisations allow researchers to do so interactively; they can explore the correspondence and its underlying graph structure in one. In the case of digital editions, it is usually not just a matter of visualising underlying data structures in the form of an ontology. The approach of an entity-based semantics visualisation is suitable for displaying the entire knowledge graph including individual entities and results from search queries. The focus is on navigation through visual structures and information acquisition (Nazemi, 2016, pp. 108–109). An example of how this can work is the Connected Papers project, which is used to search for interconnected scientific articles (Smolyansky, 2023).

Through visual representation of nodes and edges of the correspondence ontology and the different instances, researchers can navigate the interconnected entities, understand the relationships, and identify patterns or clusters within the correspondence. Contextual information can be included within the visualisation; additional metadata, annotations, or other specific details can enhance the scholarly value of the edition, leading to a richer and more informative visual representation of the entities and relationships. Since the visualised entities associate with resources on the Web, searching and exploring information could be upgraded by automatically providing all associated context based on federated queries (Nazemi, 2016, pp. 111–115). This visual exploration facilitates a more intuitive understanding of the data, enabling researchers to gain insights that might not be apparent through traditional tabular or textual representations. For non-expert users, there is no need to learn SPARQL or know about the structure of RDF

Figure 13: The Platform Connected Papers With Search Results for SemaVis. The image shows a connected graph of papers that relate to Nazemi (2016).

documents. Visual representations thus appeal to the general public; they help users to grasp key information about the correspondence and engage with it. Consequently, users can foster a broader understanding of the data basis and thus, of the correspondence. This closes the gap between information visualisation and exploratory searches: While information visualisation aims to extract visual information patterns from the data, semantic technologies such as knowledge graphs facilitate the modelling of knowledge and thus the answering of questions (Nazemi, 2016, p. 110). The entire process is human-centred, as it focuses adaptive, interactive systems that adjust their mechanisms to the users' input (Nazemi, 2016, pp. 124–127).

By providing an interactive visualisation on the website of a digital edition, the overall UX is increased. Due to actively engaging users into the content of the website, it becomes more dynamic and immersive. This way, it captures users' attention (Bleier & Klug, 2018; Warwick, 2020; Nazemi et al., 2021, pp. 477–478) and communicates the complexities of the correspondence in a more intuitive and visually appealing way.

The GUI lets the user navigate through the research material and the web presentation built around it. However, it has to be remembered that an interface [...] of a DSE is always closely linked to the data model of the underlying data and the editorial principles expressed in this data model, in that regard it is a form of pre-selective data management. Interfaces are an interpretation of knowledge and provide users with a more or less “guided tour” through the data and its general presentational setting. Furthermore, they allow the user to answer research questions and aim at supporting the generation of knowledge (Bleier & Klug, 2018, p. VII).

A visualisation, be it of data, information or knowledge, always has a persuas-

ive, manipulating effect that can be interpreted as negative and positive. Naturally, visualisations are influenced both by the persons who create them and the preceptors' interpretations; biased signals lead to biased interpretations. In the interactive visualisation of a knowledge graph and in general with all data, it should always be considered which target groups the platforms have. Researchers must be aware of the hurdles of visualisation at all times and communicate design decisions transparently (Pandey et al., 2014, pp. 2211–2213).

2.5 Text Mining for Semantic Annotation

In addition to visualising KGs and linked data on platforms of digital editions, research results can be enhanced further. In the project InfraNodus, text network analysis functions as means to obtain insights from unstructured, textual data. It helps people to get an overview of text and, with the help of a text network, bridge gaps between fragmentary concepts. With additional aid of text analysis methods like keyword or sentiment analysis, more core information can be extracted from textual input. State-of-the-art Generative Pre-trained Transformer (mostly known as the acronym GPT) workflows improve insight and visual representation of information from imported data (Korab, 2022).

Figure 14: Demo Graph Featured on InfraNodus' Website: The graph shows how words are linked together in different text inputs. A text analytical panel provides further information.

Parallel to the idea of automatically generating networks or graphs from textual data, text mining allows for semi-automatic enrichment of already existing knowledge bases. The term text mining summarises research methods and tools for extracting information from unstructured textual data. These include information retrieval techniques, natural

language processing (NLP) methods like part-of-speech tagging, keyword extraction or named entity recognition, and machine learning algorithms. Information retrieval treats ways of finding the best fitting documents for a query. Hence, the processes of information retrieval include measurements of document similarity and can be implemented based on keyword apparition (Weiss et al., 2010, pp. 75–77).

Keywords are concise descriptors of the content of a document. They help to analyse large amounts of data by indicating the main features, concepts and themes. Keyword extraction is the process in NLP of extracting such information from a document using various methods such as statistical, rule-based systems or machine learning approaches. The aim is to find a set of words that best describe the text (Siddiqi & Sharan, 2015). In relation to text mining applications, the most popular ones are opinion mining (also called sentiment analysis) or topic modelling. Sentiment analysis applications determine subjective tone and information in the form of sentiments, i.e. emotions or opinions. These are then classified with categories such as positive, negative, or neutral (Ignatow & Mihalcea, 2023b, pp. 187-198). Topic models stem from statistical models of textual data and mathematically represent themes in documents and entire document collections (Ignatow & Mihalcea, 2023a, pp. 207–220).

Figure 15: Text Mining Methods Map: The figure illustrates how different terms relate to text mining.

Text mining methods like sentiment analysis enable supplemented metadata and profound knowledge discovery. The addition of such results from analyses can close gaps in the metadata or enable entirely new perspectives on the documents (Weiss et al., 2010). This is also related to the searchability and breakdown of correspondence data in digital editions, but can also be seen globally as an advantage for exploratory searching, as this type of enrichment enables semantic searches in linked data. If interested parties conduct exploratory searches themselves, i.e. approach a data basis without prior knowledge or a concrete research question, it is profitable to offer the broadest possible

faceted indexing, particularly with topic-based access (Fähle & Sack, 2023, pp. 42–43; Düring et al., 2021; Sack, 2021, pp. 391–398, 400–401). With semantic annotation, this can be added to the knowledge graph, so that metadata about concepts (topics, sentiments, people) are further solidified. They are both human- and machine-readable and amplify findability and interpretability (Yankulov, 2023).

The result of the semantic annotation process is metadata that describes the document via references to concepts and entities mentioned in the text or relevant to it. These references link the content to the formal descriptions of these concepts in a knowledge graph. Typically, such metadata is represented as a set of tags or annotations that enrich the document, or specific fragments of it, with identifiers of concepts (Yankulov, 2023).

Adding extracted information from automatic text analysis enriches the metadata inventory. Thus, step by step, a more complete context of the knowledge graph emerges. Instead of expecting users to query information across different platforms, merging the information can provide immediate access (Schöch, 2013, pp. 87–91). This also helps to combine all results from a project in one data model and makes the data situation more transparent.

3 Data Basis

This chapter offers an introduction to and a description of the data basis of Constance de Salm's correspondence. It also includes a brief summary of some important life events and other crucial aspects about her.

3.1 The Project

The project originated at the DHIP in 2010 under direction of Prof. Dr. Gudrun Gersmann. The initial collection consisted of 7,000 letters between Constance de Salm and around 315 other people; in 1960, Baroness Montfort de Francq donated the estates to the archives of the Société des Amis du Vieux Toulon et sa Région. As members of the research group, Florence de Peyronnet-Dryden, Dr. Eva Dade, Eva Knels and Hannah Schneider set the goal of digitising and exploring the correspondence in order to make it accessible for public interest and follow-up research questions.

After indexing said collection in 2013, another one – consisting of around 3,000 letters and important family documents – was discovered in a French antiquarian bookshop. It had originally been part of the initial collection but apparently got lost when a user of the archives never returned the documents. Descendants of the Salm-Reifferscheidt-Dyck family acquired these holdings and they could be digitised at the end of 2013 with funding from the DHIP. This enabled the research group to build a digitised, extended collection of almost 11,000 documents; 10,726 are letters (originals, copies and drafts), 239 are other documents like notes or reports. Altogether, this allows new perspectives on the life and work of the poet and writer (König & Peyronnet-Dryden, 2019, see section Projekt/Der Briefbestand und das Erschließungsprojekt des Deutschen Historischen Instituts Paris and Projekt/Erweiterung des Bestandes). Simultaneously, at the University of Cologne, a group of researchers analysed the life of Constance de Salm's husband, Joseph zu Salm-Reifferscheidt-Dyck, under the lead-question of the French Revolution and its consequences, as well as the lives of aristocrats from this period (Braun et al., 2014). I give further information on this in subsection 3.4.

3.2 Constance de Salm's Letters as Gateway to Hidden or Lost Information

The letters were sent from and to Constance de Salm and around 300 other persons. Most of the correspondence took place between the Rhineland and Paris. In the extended collection, researchers can investigate numerous materials concerning a wider time range and correspondingly, they are allowed a deeper insight into how Constance

de Salm led her life.

Constance de Salm believed that her voluminous exchange of letters could be of interest to a broader audience and tried to publish them in book form. Although she had several copies prepared for her intended edition, only about thirty letters eventually made it into an edition. Despite the final edition never having seen daylight when Constance de Salm was still alive, by gathering the documents and making use of important transcripts for deciphering difficult manuscripts, the actual realisation of a finalised edition is not out of grasp anymore. The research group around Florence de Peyronnet-Dryden already laid groundwork by indexing all letters and storing the metadata in the research data management environment FuD, which was developed by the Servicezentrum eSciences at Trier University.¹⁷ Naturally, the digitisation of all available letters also plays a key role in developing an extended, publicly available edition of the correspondence. However, until 2021, the data were indeed not (yet) publicly available and people interested in the correspondence needed a user access to see the content (König & Peyronnet-Dryden, 2019, see Projekt/Der Briefbestand und das Erschließungsprojekt des Deutschen Historischen Instituts Paris).

Accordingly, in order to meet the current standards for open and FAIR data, in 2019–2021, the research group around Dr. Mareike König expanded and updated the data basis, as well as the website. Registering for accessing the website became obsolete. Digital images of the letters can be viewed without watermark. Of equal importance: During that project phase, the research group enriched metadata with norm data from GND and VIAF. For locations, the group chose GeoNames as reference. They imported all metadata concerning the correspondence into `correspSearch` and deposited it on Zenodo (König & Peyronnet-Dryden, 2019, see section Projekt/Überarbeitung, Datenkuratierung und Fairification).

The edition is still under construction and first examples can be found on DiScholEd. Nevertheless, all letters are already available for exploration on the website. With additional information like content descriptions, annotated keywords or the place of exposition with GeoNames URI, they are embedded in a conceptual and describing context. To this day, the ATRisation of the letters poses a challenge. Above all, the large amount of data, translucent writing through pages and the diversity of authors with particular handwritings make the development of a suitable ATR model an uphill battle. Other project partners, such as former DHIP-interns like Sébastien Biay who wrote his Master's thesis on a HTR-processing chain for the digital edition, mainly on the process of going from digital images to XML-TEI files, help to further upgrade

¹⁷FuD (<https://fud.uni-trier.de>) supports RDM in the humanities and social sciences and can be used by both large research associations and small research projects.

the correspondence. He also emphasises the problem of the documents being written by several people and thus trained a generic model for the recognition of these. In relation to current expectations on open data and representation of digital editions, the processing chain allows the transformation into TEI format (Biay, 2022).

3.3 Description and Stats

The subset of data that plays a key role in the following analyses and processes consists of 2,031 letters and their corresponding metadata. Only transcripts¹⁸ and originals¹⁹ of the letters are included; drafts²⁰ are not in the data basis for this analysis. This also means that I had to filter the provided metadata accordingly. The exhaustive table, as provided by Peyronnet-Dryden et al. (2021) on Zenodo, has 10,726 entries for all letters in the correspondence and 239 entries for other materials (like poems or notes).

FuD-key	last modification	document type	URL	no.	author/sender
GND (sender)	VIAF (sender)	addressee	GND (addressee)	VIAF (addressee)	date (JJJJ-MM-TT)
alternative date	place of exposition	Geonames (place of exposition)	place of reception	GeoNames (place of reception)	template
status of completeness	explanation of incompleteness	pages	beginning of letter	key contents	mentioned people
people	people	places	(places)	key words	editions
note	stock	references	digital copy: file name	recommended citation	

Figure 16: Overview of Information Given in the Metadata Table

All letters and other documents hold a unique identifier (in form of an FuD-Key and URI that also links directly to the object on the website). Main information that the table provides con-

siders senders and addressees of the letters, its date, place of exposition and the key contents. Entries for people in the correspondence (senders, addressees or otherwise mentioned persons) have, if they are listed in such data repositories, columns with GND or VIAF references. As mentioned above, Geolocations have GeoNames references. Figure 16 gives an overview of the table.

I kept all metadata information as given by Peyronnet-Dryden et al. (2021) but filtered out any letter that was not written by Constance de Salm and is a transcript or original letter. Given the focus of this explorative analysis, I also did not take a look at non-letter documents. However, the future plans include creating a pipeline that allows a subsequent expansion of the KG with more input from the tables – then also including notes, poems, and the like.

In the resulting subset, the earliest letter was sent in 1793, the last letter was sent in 1845. The frequency with which she sent letters changes over this time range of 62 years: Most documents stem from the time between 1828 and 1841. Figure 18 features

¹⁸Original in German: Abschrift.

¹⁹Original in German: Original.

²⁰Original in German: Entwurf.

Addressees and Their Frequency in the Subset

Places of Exposition and Their Frequency in the Data Basis Visualised on a Map

Figure 17: Interactive Visualisation on the Website: The visualisations – created with amCharts5 in JavaScript – show both geolocations and addressees that appear in the subset of the correspondence.

a bar chart that shows the letters' distribution of absolute frequencies.²¹

I identified 315 different addressees and seven places of expositions. Figure 17 summarises these findings.

3.4 Les Circonstances de Salm

Constance de Salm was only ‘recently’ re-discovered as a strong female lead-artist of 18th and 19th France. One example of this is that her most popular novel, *Vingt-Quatre Heures d’une femme sensible*²², was reissued in France in 2007, and a year later in paperback in Germany (Gersmann, 2014, p. 632). This is a driving force for the ongoing construction of a KG in context of this Master’s thesis. Through her letters, a portion of who and how Constance de Salm might have been becomes palpable: A networker. Friend of many. Femme philosophe.²³ A wanderer between worlds.²⁴ A mother.²⁵

Research on Constance de Salm focuses different aspects of her life and the time period in which she lived. For example, in a project of the University of Cologne, as

²¹These results also include duplicates because I automatically let the algorithm filter out any documents that are not original letters or copies but did not manually check if a copy and its original are included.

²²24 Hours in the Life of a Sentimental Woman

²³This formulation to describe CdS was taken from Colwill (2000).

²⁴This term stems from Coester (2011) and describes CdS in the German article “Wanderin zwischen den Welten? Constance de Salm, Paris und das Rheinland” by .

²⁵This is of utter importance because CdS was greatly influenced by the sudden, cruel death of her daughter Minette. Peyronnet-Dryden et al. (2021) shortly summarises the events and CdS’s reaction.

part of the Modern Academic Publishing focus group, Braun et al. (2014) published the biography of her husband, Joseph zu Salm-Reifferscheidt-Dyck, in order to present the “spaces of action and experience of the protagonist” by means of various contributions (Braun et al., 2014, see section “Zusammenfassung”). Schneider (2014) analysed how both supported each other in their own research interests — the shared passion, albeit in other areas, connected them. In this publication, letters from the DHIP’s database were also used to contextualise events and statements about Salm-Reifferscheidt-Dyck. This demonstrates how valuable the correspondence is. In addition to de Salm’s letters, which are contained in the fonds, notes and letters on the Minnette case have also been found. Clémence Pipelet, called Minnette, de Salm’s biological and Salm-Reifferscheidt-Dyck’s adoptive daughter, was shot under unknown circumstances in 1820. Thus, through the correspondence, not only Constance de Salm’s point of view but also Minnette’s thoughts and fears of the days and weeks before she was killed can be considered and explored.

Due to its volume, the correspondence as a contemporary witness allows for exploring the circumstances of the family’s, friends’ and especially CdS’s life from today’s perspective. Social and cultural references she makes herself naturally stem from the respective historical

period. This offers a glimpse into Constance de Salm’s salon, which she continued ‘virtually’ after moving from Paris to the Rhineland. On the one hand, this makes it possible to draw conclusions about the people involved in the salon society and to reconstruct the conversation in letter format. This includes a perception of how politics and social circumstances concerned 18th and 19th century France (Gersmann, 2014).

On the other hand, the correspondence reflects Constance de Salm’s state of mind and emotions at various stages of her life and accompanies her through difficult phases, such as after the murder of her daughter Minette or generally of how life in the Rhineland bored and depressed her. Her letters reflect the cultural distance between France and Germany of that time. Through her narration, it becomes possible to understand how the life of a female [!] noblewoman passed as a wanderer between two

Figure 18: Interactive Visualisation on the Website: The visualisation – created with amCharts5 in JavaScript – shows how many letters Constance de Salm sent per year, duplicates of originals and copies included.

very different cultures in turbulent times of revolution and social uncertainty (Coester, 2011; Gersmann, 2014).

[...] Constances Briefe [waren] zugleich beispielhafte Zeugnisse einer kulturellen Distanznahme: Obwohl angesichts ihrer langjährigen Aufenthalte im kulturell wie intellektuell damals aufstrebenden Rheinland der Gedanke einer intensiveren Kontaktaufnahme und Beschäftigung mit dem deutschsprachigen Literaturbetrieb nahegelegen hätte, war das Gegenteil der Fall [Constance's letters were at the same time exemplary testimonies to a cultural distancing: although in view of her long stays in the Rhineland, which was culturally as well as intellectually up-and-coming at the time, the idea of more intensive contact and engagement with the German-language literary world would have seemed obvious, the opposite was the case] (Gersmann, 2014, pp. 638).

The correspondence also opens up a view of Constance de Salm's 'feminist combat' for the self-assertion of female artists and writers in the 19th century.

In einer Zeit, in der Schriftstellerinnen und Künstlerinnen noch mit Misstrauen beäugt und vielfach öffentlich diskreditiert wurden, hat Constance de Salm als Vorläuferin einer Virginia Woolf schon seit früher Jugend immer wieder einen leidenschaftlichen Kampf um die Anerkennung der Autorinnenrechte geführt [At a time when female writers and artists were still eyed with suspicion and in many cases publicly discredited, Constance de Salm, as a predecessor of Virginia Woolf, from an early age repeatedly waged a passionate struggle for the recognition of female authors' rights] (Gersmann, 2014, pp. 638).

Maintaining her salon in the virtual, networked space of epistolary correspondence and her constant, strategic endeavour to remain up-to-date in the literary creation of Paris show that Constance de Salm always saw herself as a *femme des lettres* in her lifetime. She knew how important it was to have well-known correspondence partners and, within the framework of her salon, nurtured personal and long-distance contact with influential representatives, such as Alexander von Humboldt. The open online availability of the correspondence allows for a wide range of research on Constance de Salm's network, including same-sex and opposite-sex friendships, and underscores the complexity and importance of female exchange in Europe in the 19th and 18th centuries (Colwill, 2000, pp. 39–40).

By examining her letters, as captured by Berenguier (2017), different facets of her reality of life can be explored. Elaborating it in a KG should place the multifaceted and nuanced correspondence of Constance de Salm in a broader context. The perspectives of CdS on her environment, as well as the environmental influences and movements of

the epochs on CdS, affect each other reciprocally. She created a network in the context of the correspondence that can be coded and visualised as such on a larger, even visual level. The processing in RDF should make it possible to relate the letters to other correspondences (see, for example, the edition humboldt digital); this could also boost a development of interconnected thematic aspects in a broader framework.

A KG application could facilitate explorative search queries for the correspondence. Moreover, it would become possible to determine certain peculiarities or patterns in the correspondence. The network of correspondence can then not only be seen as such between people, but in connection with topics, emotions, places and events.

4 Main Part – Constance de Salm’s Virtual Salon Online

The main parts elaborates on the different steps of further FAIR- and LOD-ifying the correspondence of Constance de Salm. These steps include the extraction and transformation of existing metadata collections from the correspondence from proprietary into free, open formats. I also describe the ontology creation, semantic enrichment and import into a knowledge graph. Following, I explain why deciphering Constance de Salm’s letters poses a challenge for both manual and automatic transcription and present an alternative for this thesis so that some examples can be included in the semantic annotation of the KG. This chapter also outlines how I implement a first web page for the KG visualisation and point out certain design choices. The last two sections treat the steps of text mining and a final wrap-up of all previous steps.

4.1 Germany’s Next Top (Data) Model – RDFication of the Data Base

As Figure 1 shows, the first steps in the workflow include the extraction and analysis of metadata from the existing data collection and files. Metadata for the correspondence uploaded on Zenodo by the project group led by König and Peyronnet-Dryden (2019) was the basis for this.

Before filtering a subset from the spreadsheets, I converted them from the proprietary format Excel to CSV. Excel spreadsheets (XLS[X] files) are best managed through the licensed office software of Windows and are therefore not accessible to all interested parties. The choice of appropriate structures is essential for later usability and publishability of (open) data. In order to guarantee a greater number of future uses, the data should be published in different formats. The format also influences the size of a file; this is an important factor when open data are offered for download. Since open data strive to reduce barriers in regards of data usability, providing files that are easy to download quickly and – vice-versa – updated quickly when things are changed, is ideal. For data structured in rows and columns, meaning spreadsheets, this is CSV. Overall, CSV is a core format because it is open, machine-readable and supports broad reuse, making it the “lowest common denominator” for open data (European Commission & Open Data Institute, 2022; Tarrant, 2022). According to the 5-star LOD model by Berners-Lee (2006), converting data from a structured, machine-readable format like XLSX to a non-proprietary, structured format like CSV adds a third star to the data. Transforming the data into RDF is the next step.

At first, I merged the file containing information on all letters in the correspondence inventory from Zenodo (last update: 2021) with new, incoming data from FuD.²⁶ Merging different versions of collected metadata into one single file without duplicated values helps avoiding redundancy. Hence, I implemented a Jupyter Notebook that accepts CSV and XLSX files and adds them to a single dataframe.²⁷ It is important to note that given spreadsheets must share the same header format so that they can be merged without loss of data. This script directly stores the result in a CSV file.

Throughout a later stage, I normalised entries about persons, keywords and geolocations in FuD. I unified names that had affixes like ‘son of’ or ‘husband of’: For example, “comte Christophe Michel Roguet (Schwiegersohn von Jean Charles François de Ladoucette)” became “comte Christophe Michel Roguet”. I added additional information for relationships or other affixes in a new field in FuD. This was already incorporated on the correspondence’s website. However, I have not yet incorporated all unifications in the KG; this will play a role in section 6.

Generally, I filtered the merged spreadsheet according to the specifications I mentioned in section 3 and kept only letters (originals and copies) that have Constance de Salm as sender. I also extracted and added the year and decade of each letter to a new column in the spreadsheet. This is the pivotal data that later flowed into the KG.

In the following step, I created a baseline ontology for the correspondence. Ontologies are an immanent part of all cycles of linked data production and consumption (Pattueli et al., 2015, p. 269). I developed a prototypical model that re-uses existing vocabularies like FOAF and RDFS and complies with basic ideas of describing correspondences (i.e. collections of (historical) letters) in an ontology as proposed by, for example, Hyvönen et al. (2023), Cristofaro and Spampinato (2021) or Dumont (2019).

Following the example of Pattueli et al. (2015), I first specified the purpose and the scope of the ontology. I only considered metadata descriptions to be of relevance in this modelling process because I do not (yet) want to describe physical information about the letters themselves but the overall context of the correspondence’s metadata. The overall scope concerns the domain of letter correspondences. The appertaining step of knowledge acquisition involved selecting fitting vocabularies for the ontology from existing resources in order to later facilitate the process of sharing, reuse, integration and expandability (Pattueli et al., 2015, pp. 269-272). The main vocabularies I chose for this ontology are OWL, RDF, and RDFS for structural definitions like class hierarchies. Furthermore, I imported terminologies from DBPedia, GeoNames, Basic Geo (referred

²⁶Since the files on Zenodo were last updated in November 2021, a few changes that were applied in FuD in the meantime needed to be updated.

²⁷I used the Jupyter Notebook support in the Intelligent Development Environment (IDE) PyCharm. At this step, I used Python 3.8, PyCharm 2022.2 and Jupyter 1.0.0.

Figure 19: Outline of a Possible Ontology Definition: A sketch of how different entities and relationships in the ontology could describe the correspondence; the version on the bottom part of the image shows how this would act with added instances. Yellow bubbles show classes in the ontology.

to as WGS84), FOAF, and Simple Knowledge Organization System (SKOS). These are lightweight, W3C approved vocabularies that can be imported and re-used when creating an ontology. They enforce stability and facilitate interoperability by service providers and users (Pattuelli et al., 2015, p. 272). Linked Open Vocabularies provides an overview of available vocabularies.

During the next phase, the modelling phase, I consolidated the conceptual structure of the ontology, as Figure 19 illustrates. I identified key concepts, which properties they have and with which data types they need to be created, and captured the relationships. The resulting baseline ontology, also called “core model” (Pattuelli et al., 2015, p. 273), works as a glossary that contains information about all relevant umbrella concepts, relationships and properties. Also throughout this phase, I formalised the namespace for the Constance de Salm ontology, which would later identify entities and such.²⁸ I added class descriptions and restrictions to the model and formalised hierarchies (e.g. letter is of type document, decade is a literal with integer as data type, etc.). The concepts or relationships that could not be described by an existing vocabulary received a new definition in my ontology under the previously set namespace (e.g. `cds_onto:Letter`) and I nuanced between more global and more defined terms (document, keyword as super classes, letter and automatic keyword as sub classes). For doing so, I worked in Protégé, a free, open-source ontology editor and manager. Figure 20 shows an overview of the final ontology with all classes, relationships and properties. I also adjusted restrictions on properties and relationships, for example that `received_letter` can only be inserted between `letters` and `addressees`. Circles in light blue are classes from the Constance de Salm ontology; rectangles in green and light blue are self-defined, too. Circles and rectangles in other colours but those three are from external vocabularies that I listed beforehand. Figure 21 summarises definitions for the classes in the ontology.

Another subsequent phase, the generation phase, concerned the insertion of instances into the ontology, so transforming data input from the CSV spreadsheet into RDF triples. I did this using `owlready2` in Python (Lamy, 2017): It is a package for ontology-oriented programming and allows building new ontologies as well as parsing of existing ones. I realised this in a Jupyter Notebook in which the CSV file is parsed and, according to the headers of a column (intern identifier, name, GeoNames URI, etc.), the values from the row are inserted as instances or literals into the ontology. An exemplary code snippet from said Jupyter Notebook (simplified code from cell [9]) illustrates the procedure of importing letters and their features.

²⁸<https://wissen-vernetzen.github.io/ontology.html#>

Figure 20: Final Ontology Definition: A visualisation of all classes, relationships and properties in the ontology, created with WebVOWL.

```

1  def create_letter(input_url, idx, dataframe, namespace) -> onto.Letter:
2  letter = onto.Letter(re.sub(cds_docs.base_iri, '', input_url), namespace)
3  letter.fud_key = dataframe['FuD-Key'][idx]
4  letter.has_year.append(int(dataframe['year'][idx]))
5  letter.has_decade.append(int(dataframe['decade'][idx]))
6  letter.has_date.append(str(dataframe['Datierung (JJJJ-MM-TT)'][idx]))
7  return letter

```

Listing 1: Python Code for Adding Letter Instances to Graph.

The linking phase follows the generation phase; throughout it, external information joins the ontology. I did this simultaneously to the unification of data entries in the CSV file via OpenRefine before I imported most data into the ontology. In OpenRefine, I integrated URIs (URLs specifically) for all entities in the correspondence. For example, entries for Constance de Salm already had links to GND and VIAF. For other people in the correspondence, I reconciliated information based on their name from GND, VIAF and Wikidata.²⁹ The GND or Wikidata IDs became identifiers for persons; for geolocations, I chose the GeoNames ID. The keywords that were already in the

²⁹Many entries are still missing matching identifiers because they do not have a corresponding entry in any database. These entities received a URI based on the ontology's namespace.

Letter

A *letter* represents a written communication between two individuals, in this correspondence through a physical medium which is available as facsimile on the project homepage. It encapsulates properties such as sender, addressee or dates, as well as other metadata about its place of exposition, format, and any associated annotations (sentiments, keywords, etc.).

Example:

"11254"

Sender

The *sender* (in this case always Constance de Salm) represents the individual who initiates the communication via letter. It captures information about the person given by other data repositories, such as Wikidata or VIAF.

Addressee

The *addressee* represents the intended recipient of a letter. It captures information about the person given by other data repositories, such as Wikidata or VIAF.

Example:

"Jean Charles François Ladoucette@en"

Keyword

The entity *keyword* represents a descriptive term or phrase that is associated with a particular resource or concept. It provides a means to classify and organize information about the letters. The keywords were manually annotated in earlier project stages.

Example:

"santé@fr","health@en","Gesundheit@de"

Automatic Keyword

The entity *automatic keyword* represents a keyword or term that is generated automatically, typically through computational methods like text mining, intending to describe and categorise the text in the letters. It denotes a keyword that is not manually assigned by a human but is generated based on the content, context, or other relevant factors associated with the letter!

Example:

"excellent article"

Sentiment

The *sentiment* represents the emotional orientation expressed in a text or statement, capturing the overall tone, opinion, or attitude conveyed; those carry connotations such as positive, negative, or neutral.

Example:

"positive"

First Line

The *first line* represents the initial sentence of a letter. It is the beginning of the textual content and was manually transcribed in an earlier project stage.

Example:

"Voici, Monsieur, le copie de votre excellent article."

Place of Exposition

The *place of exposition* represents a location where a letter was displayed. It captures the contextual framework for the exposition, given by the name of the place, as well as geocoded information.

Example:

"Paris"

Figure 21: Class Definitions in the Ontology: Explanations as given on the website.

metadata had to be separated (each letter had an entry ‘keyword’ which summarised all keywords in a list) and subsequently received own identifiers through another round of reconciliation from Wikidata, GND, et cetera. This way, I could also add translations in English and French to the keywords, and append alternative names for Constance de Salm and other people (Pattueli et al., 2015, for methodic reference see pp. 286–288). Finally, I exported the intermediate results from Protégé in RDF/XML serialisation. I describe the final step of exploiting and publishing the data online in subsection 4.5.³⁰

4.2 Constance de Salm and the Voynich Manuscript

The Voynich manuscript consists of about 250 pages that date from the 15th or 16th century (Schinner, 2007). The pages display drawings of often unidentified plants, astronomical or astrological diagrams, and naked women bathing in “strange arrangements of pools or tubs connected by complex systems of pipes” (Schinner, 2007). The text passages are written in a script that has not yet been deciphered and therefore can not be translated in a broadly accepted manner. Several research groups have claimed to have broken the code, saying it could be Voynich-Hebrew (Hannig, 2020) or a proto-Romance language (Cheshire, 2019), but without global acceptance. Even projects with the aid of algorithms did not succeed (Hauer & Kondrak, 2016). An example page is shown in Figure 22.

Figure 22: Page 32 From the Voynich Manuscript: Image available under public domain via Wikimedia as “Voynich Manuscript (32)”.

Similarly to the Voynich manuscript, Constance de Salm’s letters are not easily decipherable. Although she did not write in an unknown language, many of her letters, however, cannot be read or transcribed either manually or automatically. For this reason, the original letters have not yet been transcribed by previous research groups, calling it “a paleographic challenge” [un défi paléographique] (Biay, 2022, p. 21). Biay (2022) tried creating

ground truths for training a model but first results showed an accuracy of only 44%. Instead, he then developed an eScriptorium pipeline for recognising, transcribing and transforming letters’ copies to XML/TEI. Some core problems remained: there are several different hands with different writing,³¹

³⁰More detailed information about code, data output, etc. can be found in the corresponding repositories that are in the GitHub repository list .

³¹eScriptorium is an open source tool for manual or automated segmentation and text recognition of historical manuscripts and prints based on the Kraken framework. It is developed by research teams

Original Letter Written by Constance de Salm: Letter CdS-b1-022m that is an example for how unreadable the manuscript is.

REGION 1
 refermé, it st eins epquraient la dauin voylant
 vou a st il dit le reuinee pur sanne lor
 troure d lacteuse.. Elles toue u pis, et
 deux têtes de feemmelites ont présenté ou au
 iteu
 vai tout le recle eclu faits aqites is u
 taut en lalie en la recnque, eet cependant
 bien reconvensante ou le lous Buis
 du fabisant de liedbi cted leelle fistan
 cerait fait tant de pectit, premd au drriuelles
 Nous tont racoule et les démonitrections
 étégient si esuryer pu jai ét ablegger la lete
 dire dun fieer - je ne pouami ve ces
 an d
 il
 lanta sívce.

 jluis de rentdavi se le ye de lud
 12
 lessi-ils disent le nessemble le qui pleits
 les plcirms renuis at pas de plait edaes
 at puil ee au recle quadux uy recuderes
 le dejeuis baur que jesle loteur, vaile, le
 pouc ausi je je sais ce feutillent d
 o
 d suirelles et des le conduit ou viens
 ne Dé
 udre en reuu sec

Automatic Transcription with Transkribus: The same letter, automatically transcribed using Transkribus Lite.

Figure 23: Comparison of Original Letter and Transcription: results generated by Transkribus Lite.

The decision not to train a model for ATR in the context of this Master’s thesis is thus based on the graphical characteristics of the sources and the fact that the time frame for this mammoth task is insufficient. Figure 23 clarifies the problem: The original manuscript is already hardly decipherable and would require expert knowledge in paleography. Equally, the output from the ATR model, that evidently has a lot of mistakes in it, can not be corrected—to create a ground truth is therefore inconceivable. From the beginning, I have made it my goal to demonstrate, also with the help of a small corpus, what potential there is in Constance de Salm’s letter correspondence. So it was also clear since then that I would only work with a few textual files, which would not require a costly, customised ATR model. Seeing that the copies are generally more legible than her original letters and can be transcribed with Transkribus Lite and a standard model for text recognition of French manuscripts, I decided to use these copies to build my ‘small corpus’.³²³³ However, I had a letter (the one from Figure 23) transcribed by a colleague from the archives of the DHIP. She is herself a native French speaker and skilled in transcribing. The handwriting of Constance de Salm posed a

at the Université Paris Sciences et Lettres (Kiessling et al., 2019).

³²Transkribus is a tool for text recognition and transcription of historical documents and its browser-based version is free for a limited number of documents (Kahle et al., 2017).

³³The model’s name is Transkribus French Model 1 and covers texts from the 17th to 20th century. It has an error rate of 7.80%.

challenge even for her, so that she was only able to transcribe just under 80%.

Copy of a Letter Written by Constance de Salm: Letter CdS-b1-022m-2.

a M. le Br de Ladoucette
 modéré et si juste que je me fais un plaisir de la transmettre à nous
 Madame et à notre digne époux et je ne doute pas que vous et lune
 Paris, ce 18 Avril 1826
 nous intéressées à Mr Vannet qui mérite les suffrages des personnes
 Je suis bien sensible, Monsieur le Baron, à l'extrême
 qui savent apprécier le talent
 amabilité avec laquelle vous m'engage à prendre place aujourd-
 Je suis charmée d'avoir cette nouvelle occasion de me rappeler à
 d'hui à votre banquet de famille. Rien ne m'aurait empêchée
 notre souvenir. Je ne suis si on vous a dit que j'ai été bien malade.
 de me rendre à cette gracieuse invitation s'il n'y avait pas in
 Je ne sais pas encore, mais je reçois quelques amis tous les soirs su
 possibilité absolue, outre que je suis horriblement entamée, j'ai aujourd'hui
 vous étiez libre jeudi de 8h à 10h, mon mari en serait aussi charmé
 3 personnes à dîner et invitées depuis 4 jours. Vous savez que je m'arrange
 que moi, car il part vendredi
 toujours pour ne pas dîner seule ce dont j'ai horreur.
 Vous parler du déménagement comme si ce n'était rien, le mot seul
 Mille et mille assurance d'amitié et de considération distinguée
 m'épouvante. Serez-vous plus près ou plus loin de moi
 que Constance de de satin
 vous aurez bien de la peine à me lire, j'ai peine à tenir la plume,
 je crois que j'ai un rhumatisme qui m'empêchera bientôt d'écrire.
 mille et mille, vieilles et nouvelles amitiés.
 signé: Constance de Salm
 Venez donc jeudi soir avec votre chère famille. J'aurai je crois,
 une dame dont je vous ai parlé.

Automatic Transcription with Transkribus: The same letter, automatically transcribed.

Figure 24: Comparison of Original Letter Copy and Transcription: results generated by Transkribus Lite.

Thus, I first selected nine copies randomly from the subset of metadata and fed the images into Transkribus Lite. Figure 24 illustrates what the original digital copy looks like and what the output of Transkribus looks like without corrections. The output is coherent and easily readable and contains only a few formatting or character errors, plus misaligned lines. Figure 25 shows the version I then corrected manually.

REGION 1
 1826
 Lettre
 (billet)
 (de Mme la
 Pcesse de Salm)
 À M. le Br de Ladoucette
 Paris, ce 15 Avril 1826
 Je suis bien sensible, Monsieur le Baron, à l'extrême
 amabilité avec laquelle vous m'engagez à prendre place aujourd-
 d'hui à votre banquet de famille. Rien ne m'aurait empêchée
 de me rendre à cette gracieuse invitation s'il n'y avait pas im-
 possibilité absolue. Outre que je suis horriblement enrhumée, j'ai aujourd'hui
 3 personnes à dîner et invitées depuis 4 jours. Vous savez que je m'arrange
 toujours pour ne pas dîner seule ce dont j'ai horreur.
 Vous parler du déménagement comme si ce n'était rien, le mot seul
 m'épouvante. Serez-vous plus près ou plus loin de moi?
 Vous aurez bien de la peine à me lire, j'ai peine à tenir la plume,
 je crois que j'ai un rhumatisme qui m'empêchera bientôt d'écrire.
 Mille et mille, vieilles et nouvelles amitiés.
 Signé: Constance de Salm
 Venez donc jeudi soir avec votre chère famille. J'aurai je crois,
 une dame dont je vous ai parlé.

Figure 25: Corrected Output from Letter CdS-b1-022m-2.

For all nine letters I proceeded identically, had them transcribed automatically and then corrected them. Then I saved the results as text files. I cleaned these up by removing the letterheads and salutations to prevent them from influencing the results too much during text mining, as they regularly occur in the same form across documents. Since the purpose of this Master's thesis is not to create an edition-worthy transcription, I did not create XML/TEI files. I explain how the text

files are processed in the text mining process in subsection 4.4.³⁴

4.3 Implementation of a First Web Page: Graph Visualisations for Beginners

In order to implement the goals of explorative, visual search in the data basis mentioned in subsection 2.4, I needed to create an interactive graph visualisation in the browser. Initially, I wanted to get an overview of the KG using Protégé’s integrated OntoGraf, but quickly realised that the tool is not well suited for large data sets, as Figure 26 illustrates. Subsequently, I imported the data as a file serialised in RDF/XML into GraphDB. This is a server-based software that allows for management of RDF data and even querying and extension of the data with SPARQL. GraphDB allows for interactive visualisations of KGs and ontologies within the local server.

I was able to create a first visualisation of the graph to get a rough idea of what the final result might look like. Figure 27 demonstrates how the visualisation is designed in GraphDB. Similar to Figure 20, both defined classes and their associated instances are shown as circles. The colours visualise the respective class. Edges denote the relationships between the entities and are given the name as a textual description.

In general, there are various software tools to display and interact with network visualisations. Desktop-based and local-server tools like Gephi are common. Gephi makes it possible to create the visual graph from a CSV file that contains information about nodes and edges (Bastian et al., 2009). Alternatively, Cytoscape also offers the possibility to read out and visualise graphs and has a few add-ons for semantic technologies like RDF (Shannon et al., 2003). Gephi can be connected to a JavaScript (JS) endpoint and allows for interactive browser applications, however, it does not take data serialised in RDF anymore.³⁵ Cytoscape.js directly offers the possibility to create JavaScript applications with graph visualisations

Figure 26: Visualisation of the Knowledge Graph in OntoGraf: too many instances are crowded in the same area.

³⁴All transcriptions can be found in this folder of my main GitHub repository. Their names resemble the last numbers of a letter’s URI, e.g. for the case in Figure 25, it is 8992.

³⁵There used to be a plugin called SemanticWebImport for this, but the Gephi team confirmed that the feature is no longer supported in current versions. The plugin can be found here: <https://seinecle.github.io/gephi-tutorials/generated-html/semantic-web-importer-en.html>.

but the RDF data beforehand must be serialised in the required JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) format (Franz et al., 2016). Exporting static image files is the simplest option in both applications.³⁶

Figure 27: Visualisation of the Knowledge Graph in GraphDB: classes and instances shown in nodes, relationships in edges.

However, to encourage the exploratory search in the correspondence’s KG – or even to stimulate it in the first place – , an interactive, overall more accessible visualisation is indispensable. Based on the visualisation in GraphDB, which is not embeddable or usable outside the server, I thus had to look for an alternative solution to the standard tools. To realise this, I determined how I could obtain a data structure usable in JS from an RDF/XML file. There were some problems with this approach: there are many libraries that visualise networks but do not accept RDF as input. There are some parsers and streams, for example the JS RDF store with SPARQL support (Garrote, 2011–2015) or the Streaming RDF/XML parser (Taelman, 2018–2023), that

can read RDF data into a JS-convenient form. Although these tools are often referred to as easy and fast access, they require very good web development skills, or at least profound experience in working with foreign frameworks. In addition, many tools have not been updated for several years (the first one, for example, has not been updated for at least seven years). The situation is similar for RDF visualisations; a lot of tools are several years old, are not regularly maintained and no longer work properly (LodLive, visualRDF). Others, like the Svelte RDF Visualisation Lab, are up-to-date but offer little opportunity for customisation in design or data parsing. Since I evidently did not have a team of web developers around me, I decided to look for software that would at least simplify the transfer of data to the website.

Upon further intensive research, I came across Neo4j, an open source graph database implemented in Java (Neo4j, 2010). Although it does not work directly with RDF but

³⁶There are no instructions for the often obsolete plugins: other users had similar concerns and requested RDF support (<https://stackoverflow.com/questions/66720/are-there-any-tools-to-visualize-a-rdf-graph-please-include-a-screenshot>), which is also discussed in this forum: <https://groups.google.com/g/cytoscape-helpdesk/c/9OSNCpH4rZ0?pli=1>.

Figure 28: Neo4j Labeled Property Graph: nodes and edges of the correspondence in Neo4j Bloom.

with labelled property graphs, it was a welcome solution. Labeled property graphs (LPGs) and RDF are both structures that describe data in graph-like form. Nevertheless, they differ in core data modelling, schemas and query languages. LPGs define graphs as nodes, edges and properties instead of in subject-predicate-object triples like within RDF. Entities and relationships can have flexible, varying properties that are less dependent on a fixed schema. The common query language for LPGs is Cypher instead of in SPARQL. Both frameworks are often described as competing because they bring different advantages and disadvantages that determine which is more suitable in a given use case. I do not want to compare LPGs with RDF triple databases; in this project, RDF is important as part of the Semantic Web and thus as the basis of the KG. However, there is a larger, well-documented set of tools for managing and visualising LPGs in Neo4j, which economised the development of the interactive visualisation.

Neo4j offers graph database management systems a browser and desktop clients. There are paid licences for larger projects and companies (enterprise version). Private, smaller-scale use (community version) is possible free of charge. Neo4j Desktop provides the ability to manage multiple databases on a local server. In the browser, the cloud service Neo4j AuraDB allows one running instance – that can be accessed from anywhere – in the free version. Both applications are extensively described in the official

documentation and in the apps themselves, Neo4j offers tools for getting started, for managing extensions and visualisations. There are also cheatsheets and instructions for the query language Cypher.

With the extension *neosemantics* (mostly referred to as *n10s*) (Barrasa & Cowley, 2017), a semantics toolkit, it is possible to import RDF data and associated vocabularies like OWL, RDFS, SKOS, and more into Neo4j. Imports can be serialised in RDF/XML, JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data (JSON-LD) or similar.

I started by importing the RDF/XML file of the Constance de Salm KG into a local Neo4j graph database. The Cypher query required for the import, as well as the configurations required to load the underlying ontology and individual entities, are described in the documentation by Barrasa and Cowley (2017). After a successful data import, the LPG's content is displayed in a corresponding tab (as list of nodes, edges and properties). As shown in Figure 28, the integrated tool Neo4j Bloom then presents the data as visual graph. Similar to previous figures like Figure 20, nodes and edges are visualised as circles and lines connecting them. Nevertheless, in contrast to the RDF graph, the LPG stores properties of entities stored directly within them and not as separate edges, thus visualising them in a corresponding field.

Another integrated tool is NeoDash, which makes it possible to display statistics on the data situation. In such a dashboard, which is automatically created in the browser for a local graph database, for example, the number of certain classes and even calculations with properties can be visualised. Figure 29 illustrates what a dashboard would look like for an exemplary data set. NeoDashes run on a local server and can be built and published for read-only access but they can not be embedded directly on a website.

Next to NeoDash, Neo4j supports other visualisation frameworks that run in classic JS and front-end JS libraries like React.js or Vue.js. These embeddable tools with built-in Neo4j connections are, for example, Popoto.js or Neovis.js. Both tools enable different types of graph visualisations.

Neovis.js is mainly focused on providing interactive force-directed graph visualisations similarly to Gephi, but also algorithms for other layouts (e.g., PageRank). Popoto.js in contrast helps users build queries in a visual way that can be executed against Neo4j data. Results are customisable on the interactive website. There is an option for auto-complete searches and Cypher translations. A web page with Popoto.js could look like in Figure 30. This kind of visualisation supports users in querying the data and therefore the paradigm of exploratory search, but an overall grasp of the KG is not possible. In addition, for both frameworks, a connection to a Neo4j server would require me to redirect it via an application programming interface (API) port that is

Figure 29: NeoDash Demo Application: The dashboard summarises data about the domain names registered for New Caledonia.

not accessible from the client-side.³⁷³⁸

Instead, I have chosen a framework that has no need for server connections and is in 'pure' JS. Libraries such as D3.js provide the ability to embed graph visualisations into a web page without connecting directly to an underlying Neo4j database. This avoids the problem of client-side access and redirects data sent from the database. I chose D3.js because it promises customisable, dynamic visualisations and provides a forum with examples for many use cases, such as networked data with simulated forces (Bostock, 2012). Having said that, the results are formatted differently to Neo4j and need to be transformed accordingly. GitHub user eisman (2017) has implemented a framework (neo4jd3.js) that makes the Neo4j data format compatible with D3.js, and allows a force-directed graph visualisation to be generated from that data.

To feed the data into this framework, I had to download it from the local Neo4j database, formatted as shown in Figure 32. Downloading a lot of data in JSON format requires querying the database with an API platform. I used Postman to create a REST (REST stands for Representational State Transfer) API call to the local server and retrieve the data in the correct format. REST APIs follow the principles of the REST

³⁷An API facilitates communication between a user and a system by defining a set of rules for how applications or devices can connect to and communicate with each other. See more in this article by IBM: <https://www.ibm.com/topics/rest-apis>.

³⁸This is so that non-authorized users can not access the back-end information (like the server password) from Neo4j. Other users proposed how to implement this in Neovis.js and shared the code via GitHub (<https://github.com/neo4j-contrib/neovis.js/issues/265>), but since I do not have any experience with back-end servers in JavaScript, I decided against giving this a try.

Figure 30: Popoto.js Demo Application: The dashboard shows a restaurant data set sample.

architectural style and are a common way of connecting components and applications in a microservices architecture.³⁹

I embedded the extracted JSON file into the neo4jd3.js application and created a first graph visualisation with JS, HyperText Markup Language (HTML) and Cascading Style Sheets (CSS). In this visualisation it is possible to interact with the different nodes (drag, zoom, pin, etc.) and display an info box by hovering over them, as shown in Figure 32. In addition, the nodes can be personalised with icons and images, as well as different colours, font sizes, etc. (using the D3.js framework in the background). I then embedded this first visualisation into the website, the implementation and realisation of which I explain in section 5.

4.4 Text Mining on Constance de Salm's Letters

For the text mining part of this workflow, I created a Jupyter Notebook in which I used external libraries in Python to extract content from the different letters and their first lines.

I followed the tutorial by Kaewnoparat (2023) for the keyword analysis, which explains how to extract focal information from French reviews. The algorithm starts

³⁹For more, see this article by IBM: <https://www.ibm.com/topics/rest-apis>.

```

{
  "results": [
    {
      "columns": ["user", "entity"],
      "data": [
        {
          "graph": {
            "nodes": [
              {
                "id": "1",
                "labels": ["User"],
                "properties": {
                  "userId": "eisman"
                }
              },
              {
                "id": "8",
                "labels": ["Project"],
                "properties": {
                  "name": "neo4jd3",
                  "title": "neo4jd3.js",
                  "description": "Neo4j graph visualization using D3.js.",
                  "url": "https://eisman.github.io/neo4jd3"
                }
              }
            ],
            "relationships": [
              {
                "id": "7",
                "type": "DEVELOPES",
                "startNode": "1",
                "endNode": "8",
                "properties": {
                  "from": 1470002400000
                }
              }
            ]
          }
        }
      ]
    }
  ],
  "errors": []
}

```

Figure 31: Format for Neo4jD3.js Application: information about nodes and edges is stored in a JSON-like structure.

Figure 32: Visualisation Generated With Neo4jD3.js: The interactive visualisation shows exemplary data from GitHub user eisman; in the left upper corner, a hovered node's infobox is visible.

with a tokeniser from sklearn (`CountVectorizer`) (Pedregosa et al., 2011) that adapts according to the input text. Accordingly, the implementation converts the input to a matrix of token counts, a numerical representation of the text that is machine-understandable. This initial step does not consider stop words like “un” (a) or “ce” (this).

Albeit, Kaewnoparat (2023) recommends removing stop words, which are some of the most common, short function words, and keeping only the most meaningful ones for keyword extraction. I proceeded to download a stop word list from the Natural Language Tool Kit, which is a Python module for natural language processing (Bird et al., 2009). Using a hyperparameter with the list as value, the `CountVectorizer` can then filter out stop words. With spaCy's part-of-speech tagger (Honnibal et al., 2020), I filtered out unnecessary parts of speech and kept only nouns (NOUN).

As a last step and to eliminate further words from the result set, I let the implementation calculate the distance of each token from the original text and kept those three with the smallest result. Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (mostly called BERT for short) can calculate the similarity

	keyword_list	keywords_full-letter
<u>V/11252</u>	['matin', 'éducation', 'pétition']	['j'ai repensé', 'cher voisin', 'disiez hier']
<u>V/11245</u>	['monsieur', 'arrivée', 'lettre']	['n'est qu'aujourd'hui', 'peux enfin', 'fort sensible']
<u>V/8992</u>	['monsieur', 'baron', 'amabilité']	['l'extrême amabilité', 'm'aurait empêchée', 'horriblement enrhumée']
<u>V/11254</u>	['copie', 'monsieur', 'article']	['excellent article', 'mieux raisonné', 'mieux écrit']
<u>V/8994</u>	['peine', 'maladie', 'accablée']	['charmant dessin', 'l'y placer', 'mis près']
<u>V/9858</u>	['madame', 'saison']	['saison s'avance', 'quelques mots', 'j'espère pouvoir']
<u>V/11249</u>	['monsieur', 'jours', 'lettre']	['quelques lignes', 'quoiqu'il n'ait', 'm'est insupportable']
<u>V/11256</u>	['choses', 'monsieur', 'moment']	['souffrante hier', 'n'ai pu', 'qu'une partie']
<u>V/11244</u>	['edition']	['j'avais oublié', 'cher voisin', 'petite edition']

Figure 33: Table of Keywords for Transcribed Letters and First Lines: The first lines have three single tokens, the entire transcriptions a list of three two token key phrases.

between textual input (so-called documents). (Reimers & Gurevych, 2020). They transform documents or words in mathematical embeddings; these embeddings (one for the original text, the others for the results from previous extraction steps) are compared with each other sequentially. Each token from the result list receives a distance value that resembles how different it is from the original text; small distances show better representativeness of a token for its proximity to the original meaning.

For the nine transcriptions and all the first lines of the letters, I followed the same steps. For the first lines, I extracted up to three keywords (if possible). I found that the single token results for the full transcriptions were not sufficient (repetitions of only “monsieur”, “voisin” and the like), so I switched to a different implementation of Multilingual Rapid Automatic Keyword Extraction for Python (Rose et al., 2010) and

created two token-long key phrases instead. The rake implementation does not remove stop words. The algorithm transfers all results to a corresponding column and row in a CSV table for metadata (the one created in subsection 4.1); Figure 33 is an extract from the table that shows the results for the transcriptions and their first lines. The transcriptions thus have two keyword entries, the remaining, non-transcribed letters currently only have keywords for their first lines.⁴⁰ Figure 33 presents the results for the transcriptions and the first lines. The results more or less match the key content of the letters. For the following analysis, I will take letter 11244 as an example:

[...] *J'avais oublié, mon cher voisin, les 2 exemplaires de ma petite Edition*
 [...]. J'ai aussi une autre chose passée à vous expliquer, mes mauvais yeux ne me permettent pas encore de sortir, vous me trouvez donc avant, pendant, et après le dîner et tout la soirée. Venez donc si cela vous est possible, ou en plus tard demain de bon matin, je suppose à 9 h mais aujourd'hui vaudrait mieux [...]. [I had forgotten, my dear neighbour, the 2 copies of my small Edition; but I had them sent to you this morning; I think it will not be too late for them to be sent. I also have another thing to explain to you in the past, my bad eyes do not allow me to go out yet, so you can find me before, during and after dinner and all evening. Please come if you can, or early tomorrow morning, I suppose at 9 o'clock but today would be better.]

	first-line_sentiment	sentiment
t/11252	5 stars	negative
t/11245	1 star	neutral
t/8992	5 stars	neutral
t/11254	5 stars	positive
t/8994	1 star	positive
t/9858	5 stars	neutral
t/11249	5 stars	positive
t/11256	5 stars	neutral
t/11244	3 stars	neutral

Figure 34: Table of Keywords for Transcribed Letters and First Lines: The first lines have three single tokens, the entire transcriptions a list of three two token key phrases.

This example shows a special feature of Constance de Salm's letter beginnings: they are mostly extensive and are accordingly also suitable for a keyword analysis. Central to this example is the keyword "edition", which Constance de Salm mentions last. It corresponds to de Salm's intention in sending this letter, since she forgot to send her edition to the correspondent Ladoucette. For the full transcription, the key phrases are "j'avais oublié", "cher voisin" and "petite edition" – a result that overlaps with the impression of the first sentence which shows that in general, the keywords reflect the most important words in the transcribed letters and their first sentences. Since the result sets partly overlap, this could hint at a special importance of the first lines of the letters. Yet, as this

is only an experimental sample, not all letters can be covered and elicited. I give a further outlook and more extensive discussion on the algorithm, the available modules

⁴⁰The same applies to the sentiments.

in Python and the results in section 6.

For the sentiment analysis, I used Textblob for French (Loria, 2018), as well as the DistilCamemBERT model (Delestre & Amar, 2022), which is a state-of-the-art language model for French. Similarly to the procedure for keyword extraction, the script reads in input from the first lines and the complete transcriptions. Depending on the implementation, the script assigns different values to the sentiments. The CamemBERT model notates one to five stars (like in an online shopping rating system), which represent the scale terrible to excellent appreciation. In Textblob, there are three basic sentiments, negative (-1), neutral (0) and positive (1). I tested the CamemBERT model on all the first sentences, and Textblob for the nine transcriptions. I later also modelled how the different sentiment notations correspond in the KG. The results, partly shown in Figure 34, are again divided into first lines and transcribed letters. The results are relatively dissimilar between the first lines and the complete transcriptions. The discrepancy is particularly great in letter 11252 and letter 8994: the beginnings of the letters have a completely opposite connotation compared to the rest of the letter.

[...] *J'ai repensé ce matin, mon cher voisin, à ce que vous me disiez hier sur une pétition que l'on vous propose de faire en faveur de l'éducation des femmes:* [...] d'abord que je suis encore si souffrante et si accablée qu'il me serait bien impossible de lire ou de ne faire lire votre ouvrage, et de vous dire avec quelques détails ce que j'en penserai et ensuite que j'ai dans ce moment tant de choses à faire pour publier mon Edition que je suis à peine, si mes vieilles forces pourrait y suffire. [...] [I have been thinking this morning, my dear neighbour, of what you said to me yesterday about a petition you propose to make in favour of women's education: [...] first that I am still so ill and so overwhelmed that it would be quite impossible for me to read your work or to have it read, and to tell you in some detail what I think of it, and secondly that at the moment I have so many things to do to publish my Edition that I am hardly sure whether my old strength could suffice.]

The extract of letter 11252 is an example of this phenomenon. It showcases why the beginning is associated with a rating of five stars, i.e. an extremely positive sentiment, whereas the rest of the letter is rather neutral, leaning towards negative. The emphasised quotation shows the first sentence where Constance de Salm tells her correspondent that she has thought about what he told her about a proposed petition on women's education. This positive connotation suggested by the algorithm probably stems from phrases like "dear neighbour" or "favour of women's education". In the rest of the letter, de Salm justifies that she hardly gets to read his work because of her poor health and the amount of work she still has to do for her edition. A negative intonation is therefore quite apparent. Much like the keywords, there is already a tendency in the letters that

can be analysed through the sentiments. However, it is only with a larger number of samples that clearer trends or patterns emerge when textual phenomena are extracted.

4.5 Putting It Together: Text Mining Results Meet the Graph

Before unifying all results on the website, I still had to integrate the newly extracted information for the letters in the KG. To do so, I added two new classes to the baseline ontology, namely ‘automatic keyword’ and ‘sentiment’. These new classes are connected to the letters and first lines with the relationships ‘has_ _sentiment’ and ‘has_ _automatic-keyword’.

Using a similar implementation as in subsection 4.1, I added the results to the KG (see Figure 35 for comparison). I

added the different keywords and sentiments to the KG without duplicates and created an instance for each of them. I then added them to the letters and first line instances using one of the two relationships. In Neo4j, through this approach, intersections between first lines or letters with the same results emerge (see Figure 36). This process of semantic annotation opens up further connections between the documents that exist beyond sender and addressee.

Figure 35: New Classes in Ontology: automatic keywords and sentiments.

Figure 36: Letters, Keywords and Sentiments in Neo4j: The sentiments and keywords newly connect different letters.

5 From Idea to Website

The final step in the workflow is to gather all the information together on a public website. As a result, the website shall allow exploratory access to Constance de Salm's correspondence and the KG. It should function as an entry point and a different kind of index search navigation system for those outside the domain. Including an interactive visualisation of the KG aims to improve usability, intuitive exploration, discoverability of contextual information, UX and communication outside the 'expert bubble'. Embedded in a multi-content website, the graph visualisation is supposed to interact with contextual content around it for better understanding and reusability.

Although the final product is not a complete digital edition, the idea belongs to the context of DSEs and their appearance as web interfaces. Research on interface design for DSEs (of correspondences), like proposed by Dumont (2018), declares that letters and their heterogeneous content need a digital representation that helps modern readers – alias users – to determine the position of an object in a greater collection of letters and other documents in order to prevent having to read all of them. Particularities of letters play an important role in the process of designing a DSE and the corresponding user interface. Ideally, GUIs of DSEs are mirrors of their users' requirements and the underlying data (models) (Bleier & Klug, 2018; Dumont, 2018, pp. 111–112).

The design of the GUI influences the message that is transferred to users, the users' experience and the popularity of a DSE (Andrews & van Zundert, 2018). Based on the flexibility that is available digitally, GUIs of DSE need to surpass the "printed page paradigm" (Sahle, 2013a), the phenomenon in which researchers try to mimic printed editions on the web, and get involved with the vast amount of possibilities given in the digital form. As a result, and also influenced by the fact that the medium 'online' is still relatively new for DSEs, digital editors experiment with different ways to design and create graphical user interfaces. Therefore, there are no set design principles for user interfaces of digital scholarly editions. Innovative layouts in such GUIs require knowledge about general design processes of software or websites: usability and UX, but also patterns and principles, as well as feedback on user requirements (Pietro & Turco, 2018).

Since there are no fixed design specifications, I have joined the ranks of other researchers who are taking an experimental approach to this. In doing so, I was guided by general standards on usability, UX and design principles, as well as considering what statement the website should ultimately make (Shneiderman et al., 2006). I used HTML/CSS/JavaScript for developing the final website and followed design principles that relate to layout, hierarchy, colour, typography and the like. The following subsection explains all relevant approaches.

5.1 Web Design

For designing the website, the first question to consider is what scope it encompasses and what the user's goals in using this specific interface are. As I already outlined in this section's introduction 5, ultimately, the goal is to build an entry point for non-expert users to the correspondence of Constance de Salm, using an interactive visualisation of the KG for exploratory research within letters and such. Designing and building such a website requires planning, a user-centered approach, and consideration of the specific needs of researchers and scholars.

This initial step of brainstorming includes an analysis of existing platforms and potential future users. Drawing inspiration from various DSEs, I researched design elements and content structures that resonated with my field of study. To do so, I evaluated texts from the review journal for digital editions and resources (short title: RIDE) with a focus on navigation and search, plus my own experience with DSEs.

In his review of the *Briefe und Texte aus dem intellektuellen Berlin um 1800* (Baillot, n.d.), Grabsch (2020) criticises first of all that the font size and colour score poorly in terms of usability and accessibility, as the text is too small and not easy to read. In addition, although full text search is possible, it does not always work and there are frequent errors. He emphasises that a working (full-text) search is a crucial feature for a digital edition project, as it creates new access possibilities.

The site is currently in a similar state; when I did a full-text search, I did not receive any error messages in the browser, but if no suitable match was found, the results were downloaded as a file with an unclear format that contains the error code in HTML.

Kurz (2020) notes in the review of *Briefwechsel zwischen August Sauer und Bernhard Seuffert 1880 bis 1926* (Fetz et al., 2020) that navigation is only possible via the letters themselves and that a search is only possible within the person index. Mentions in the text have to be searched for in a complicated way, as there are no links back.

As the site does not look the same now as it did at the time of the review, I can only limitedly compare. When Kurz reviewed the website there was a search function directly on the home page, which allowed access to the edition via an index. However, in the current version there is no search bar on the home page, only in the index of persons. A full-text search is therefore not possible; only set subjects [Themenlinien] can be viewed and used as a filter.

Both reviews conclude that such shortcomings lead to a reduction in usability and that users are put to unnecessary extra trouble when certain basic functionalities are missing.

Equipped with these insights, I carefully planned the architecture of the website and created a sketch that outlines the navigation and logical progression of content. I also

Figure 37: Persona for Interface Design: The persona Vincent Graham that will guide the design process of the website.

chose the URL during this phase: as the KG is the driving force behind this project, I chose its ontology domain specification as the website's URL.⁴¹

Design patterns for interfaces originate in aspects of perceptual psychology in human-computer interaction and aid to make platforms more aligned with their needs and behaviours. A key feature when designing and implementing UIs are the usability principles. They are heuristics that help to make interfaces more accessible, user-friendly and intuitive and encompass learnability, efficiency, memorability, flexibility, error tolerance, consistency, feedback, clarity, visibility, accessibility, aesthetics and minimalism (Matera et al., 2006). The consideration of behavioural patterns and application of design principles contribute to enhancing the overall UX. Because of this inevitable intertwining of behavioural patterns and design principles with UX and usability, I will explain the design process of the website hand in hand with examples of different principles that I used for the actual implementation.

First, I created a persona to guide me through the design process. A persona is a design technique that captures key aspects of a presumed future user group. The persona in question, shown in Figure 37, is Vincent Graham, a 27-year-old who works as a research assistant in Luxembourg.

⁴¹wissen-vernetzen.github.io [connecting-knowledge in English].

Figure 38: Central Aspects of Expectations Towards the Website: List of requirements and the like the persona Vincent has.

Vincent as a persona is ideal to portray the aims of my website because he is not an expert but still wants to know more about correspondence. He sums up a general group of users: not all of them may have absolutely no experience with DSEs, but most (new) users will not know in detail about Constance de Salm and her correspondents and therefore little idea of what to look for. Accordingly, I created a list, inspired by Tidwell (2006), that centralises all important website, content and interaction features corresponding to what someone like Vincent would need (see Figure 38).

Secondly, I consulted behavioural patterns for interactive design in order to theoretically consolidate user goals for the website. They summarise cognition and common behaviour in terms of human-interaction with (software) interfaces and are derived from user observations. They are the basis for efficient interface design elements; an interface that supports these patterns helps users to achieve their goals more effectively. These patterns also provide methods for an enhanced UX design. They include safe exploration (users can explore without suffering negative consequences (from mistakes)), instant gratification (users receive instant results from interactions), or habituation (website offers users a defined set of known tools for interactions) (Tidwell, 2006). These behavioural patterns are the basis for most (interaction) design decisions. Along with context they organise how to develop the final product.

Multipurpose Dashboard as Provided by Neuro.

Dashboard Mockup for wissen-vernetzen.github.io

Figure 39: Comparison of Multipurpose Dashboards: an example by Neuro. and my own dashboard mockup.

Third, I began to design the information space of the entire website. According to Tidwell (2006), the information architecture combines obtained knowledge in terms of user requirements, the content's structure, possible navigation and browsing experiences, as well as a workflow for tasks. It is the practice of effectively organising content. Hence, it also involves design sketches for the website (Rosenfeld & Morville, 2007). During this step, I also collected and created further content for the website (besides the KG): I created the interactive diagrams from Figure 17, composed an ontology definition and the introduction text. I also wrote short texts that give additional information on the website's purpose and a guide for doing research within the graph.

Exploratory searching involves the discovery and investigation of information, making it vital to create an intuitive and efficient platform that facilitates exploration and analysis (Rosenfeld & Morville, 2007, section 6.2.1.3.). The website's structure therefore relies on how the KG is organised and how it provides information for exploration: the main focus lies on an interactive visualisation of nodes and edges. Alongside the KG, I want to provide side information about the correspondence and statistics that summarise the corpus at a glance; this helps novices to orientate themselves on the site. To give users a clear entry point, I decided to display the introduction text as one of the first elements.

In order to adequately structure the content on the entire website and the homepage in particular, I considered visual hierarchy and corresponding layout patterns. Layout, defined as the way in which elements are arranged, influences how users perceive and navigate the website. Layout patterns that create visual hierarchies of the website's

content guide users directly to the most important parts. A clear navigation menu, titled sections (different sections of content receive their own titles; this aids with chunking information into being more processable), and logical categories and subcategories, further solidify this. Collapsible and expandable modules, such as accordion bars, facilitate overall navigation and orientation on the website and avoid overcrowding. Composition and position, colour, density, alignment and grids all have an impact of how the website's content is perceived (Tidwell, 2006, see pp. 29, 135–143, 209–221, 255–275).

A possibility to structure research data and information in such a hierarchical page is the dashboard pattern. A dashboard is a platform that displays key data points in a single information-dense page, including visualisations like charts and graphs. They are usually used in business for providing bundled information to employees. The main architecture of a dashboard includes components like titled sections, lists and tables, and information graphics (Tidwell, 2006, pp. 77–80). Since dashboards gather important information, they are suitable for the requirements of the *wissen-vernetzen* website. Dashboards are based on design patterns of visual design and hierarchy in such a way that key information is presented centrally.

Figure 39 shows a comparison of a typical dashboard platform as provided by Neuro. and my first homepage mockup. I created the mockup (and others that are in the appendix under Figure 50–Figure 52) during the design phase of the website development. Once again, I used design principles to govern the visual elements I incorporated, such as colour scheme, typography, layout and overall interface design.

The global structure follows the previously introduced dashboard pattern; content is chunked by its category (introduction, charts for overview, KG visualisation) and separated in cards. Cards are UI components that contain information unified by common traits. In regards of visual hierarchy and relation between the elements, I followed recommendations that concern colour, size and position in order to make important parts stand out on the website. Gestalt principles—proximity, similarity, continuity and closure—influence how important and relational visual elements are perceived (Tidwell, 2006, p. 217). Hence, I put the overview charts together in one grid, the card with the introduction text on the left on its own. Through similar size, I accentuated the connection between the chart visualisations. In order to not disturb a continuous flow of the website and increase alignment, I made the introductory card resemble a side bar that follows the reading direction from the beginning (chart cards) in direction of the KG. I tried to reduce effects of proximity and closure—users' perception interpreting shapes in spaces where no shapes are intended—by using low contrast between the background and the card elements, as well as higher margin between them

(negative space).

The composition highlights focal points of the website that users should follow. Principles of visual hierarchy and arrangement also aid with visual flow, so in what order users perceive the content of the page (e.g. from top to bottom, starting left with the introduction text and the KG last). The UI regions are separated not only by cards for the content but also by header, menu and navigation bar, the main content area and the footer (Tidwell, 2006, p. 225). As the topmost section, the header is the global navigation and information space of the website. In the mockup, it comprises the website's logo, the logos of different institutions associated with the project and a (collapsed) menu. In this mockup, said menu is on the right side. The main content area takes up most of the space and is framed at the bottom by the footer, which includes secondary information for the website (legal notice, links to templates, etc.). I intended to create a balanced layout by distributing elements evenly, so that the website's design feels more harmonious. Except for the KG card that has a pop-up window displaying additional information for a clicked node that overlaps other elements of the page, all other elements are aligned in a similar style (rounded cards in the same colour and similar sizes). The cards are all collapsible (orange button on the right or bottom).

This dashboard is the homepage of the website. I also included other modules/pages for side information. For example, an extensive description of the graph's underlying ontology or a detailed project description are on a separate page, like Figure 40 visualises. These pages can be accessed via links on the homepage (for example in the introduction text) or the navigation bar.

For the overall design in header, main part, navigation and footer, I stuck to simple colours and fonts and tried to maintain a consistent visual style that creates a cohesive UX. Continuous and simple colours should also aid with an increased accessibility, ensuring that all users, including those with disabilities, can access the website (Tidwell, 2006, pp. 257–262).

I chose the colour from the DHIP logo as a main colour for the logo and titles of the website and oriented all other shades around it; for the background, I opted for a light grey, the cards are displayed in a darker shade of grey. The orange is relatively high saturated to make sure that it is readable in contrast to the light background. Other text, for example in the cards' bodies, are in black. Font-wise, I chose a display typeface in cursive that mainly works for larger elements, i.e. the logo. The rest of the textual elements are displayed in a sans serif font because these tend to have a more contemporary look and hold their legibility at smaller sizes. For the mockup, I chose the font sizes dependent on the category (header, title, body) but generally kept title sections and important text in a larger font. The choice of colour and font influences

Figure 40: Project Description Page: subpage of the website on which the project and other things are explained in detail.

readability and the emotional message of the content: colours and typefaces have distinct “voices” which have an impact of how the text is read by potential users. For example, serif fonts often convey an old-fashioned feeling (Tidwell, 2006, pp. 274–276).

Furthermore, I also included icons (for example in the KG card, a lightbulb) to convey information instead of a textual representation (Tidwell, 2006, pp. 277–279). In this case, hovering over the lightbulb displays further information on the KG’s functionality. Buttons, for example the button for searching in the graph, has the familiar magnifier as icon and a concrete description of the possible interaction (“search in graph”).

The design patterns I have chosen aim to improve the usability and UX of the website. Especially aspects like layout and content that are divided into sections with headings and subheadings and follow a common theme allow for quick discovery of relevant information. The choice of colours, text and navigability of the different modules enhance usability and promise to reinforce behavioural patterns. All these points intend to make users feel comfortable using the site and prevent that they have to search indefinitely for content. Clear headings, subheadings and a global content hierarchy help users understand the relationships between different elements and find the information they need easily. Overall, visual aesthetics positively impact UX: a positive first impression influences how users react to the site and whether they return to it or close the window for good. Design choices also significantly affect interactions,

as they can influence how users engage with content and offered functionalities. Visual cues given by colour, contrast or size do not only influence usability but can direct the user's attention to specific areas or prompts (buttons, icons) on the website and encourage the user to take the desired action (Tidwell, 2006, pp. 27–39, 374–382).

Figure 41: Search in Graph Workflow: prototypical interaction workflow of how a user would search in the KG.

Such actions need to be planned in advance so that functionality and visual design work harmoniously (Tidwell, 2006, pp. 1–10, 374–382). In a fourth and final design phase, I also created a prototypical workflow for explorative search in the KG. The tasks need to be solvable by both novices and experts and therefore require clear structuring and explanation

on the website. In general, the action is structured as shown in Figure 41: A user like the persona Vincent could search for a keyword like 'health' or a place like 'Paris' and type it into the search box. If the graph contains a relevant entry, the implementation filters it accordingly. If not, the browser displays an error message. Once a suitable result was found, the user could double-click on the displayed nodes and expand the contextual nodes, or reload the entire graph. Just as the design should support and not interfere with usability and UX, the search process within the graph should support behavioural patterns. This means, among other things, that the user can navigate within the graph without the website crashing, or that the search corresponds to the usual standards of a web search (the user enters text and receives a suitable answer relatively quickly, or a message if there are no results for the search). The exact implementation of this interaction schema follows during the deployment of the actual website.

Thinking about an interaction workflow schematically before implementation can ensure control over how users interact with the elements on the website and how they achieve their intended goals (Tidwell, 2006, pp. 374–382), such as searching in the KG or finding information about the project. The website design I have developed aims to

provide a user-friendly and effective interface. Overall, the design process involved steps of research, method planning, a combination of planned interaction workflows, and the study and application of design principles. Whether or not the design lives up to the expectations concerning UX or usability can only be fully tested after implementation.

5.2 Web Development

The web development phase begins with the choice of an appropriate web development platform. Currently, the facsimiles and indexed information on the letters of Constance de Salm are hosted on the official website that is based on WordPress. For this reason, I tried to implement a HTML page that could be embedded there.

Unfortunately, WordPress can be quite cumbersome

when it comes to the inclusion of custom web content. Although there are certain plugins and frameworks that allow embedding, many things are not possible without a lot of effort: this includes reading in data via a server or downloading modules that are necessary for visualisations. In addition, the available WordPress instances for testing run via a Hypotheses server, which does not allow necessary plugins to be installed without further ado.⁴²

It would be possible to create a web application for WordPress with Vue.js or React.js (or other, modern JavaScript frameworks);⁴³ however, the necessary plugins for this are also missing.

After assessing my own skills, resources and especially the timeframe of this Master's thesis, I decided to implement a standalone website based on HTML/CSS and JavaScript

Figure 42: Components of the Website: Overview of the different components that I built for the website.

⁴²Hypotheses is a non-commercial blog portal for the humanities and social sciences. More, especially concerning plugins, can be read here

⁴³Further information is provided on the following pages for Vue.js and React.js.

Figure 43: NiceAdmin Bootstrap Template: default version of the dashboard.

and postpone the embedding in WordPress to a later moment in time. I have been using GitHub to manage all project-related data; this led me to the conclusion that GitHub Pages would be a suitable solution. GitHub Pages is a static hosting site that pulls HTML, CSS, and JavaScript files directly from a repository on GitHub, optionally runs them through a build process, and publishes a website. This way, other data for the project, like JSON files or the like, can also directly be included in the website's deployment. For the different components of the website, shown in Figure 42, I followed a number of implementation steps.

First of all, I searched for a fitting bootstrap example. Bootstrap is a free frontend framework and includes HTML and CSS-based design templates for typography, forms, buttons, tables, grids, navigation and other design elements. JavaScript extensions can also be included. Accordingly, there are also templates for dashboards. Some bootstrap offerings are paid, but I searched for a free template and used the template that is called *NiceAdmin – Free Bootstrap Admin HTML Template* (see Figure 43).⁴⁴ The NiceAdmin template allows for a number of different functionalities and visualisations. The home page is the dashboard, other pages accessible from the menu offer other components (forms, tables, icons, etc.).

I downloaded the available files and created a GitHub repository and project page for the wissen-vernetzen website. In order to be able to use the domain name, I made a GitHub organisation with the same name because usually, GitHub Pages sites use the username as default domain (except for when people have bought a custom domain that can be used). In a new repository, I deposited the dashboard project files from NiceAdmin and deployed the website for a first test run. The test run worked and

⁴⁴The template can be found here.

Figure 44: Adapted Template: including introduction text and charts.

displayed the template with sample content.⁴⁵

Following, I adapted the dashboard's design to the previously created drafts from subsection 5.1. To do this, I removed all unusable components from the website and only kept the dashboard, as well as the FAQ and Contact pages. I adjusted the colours to the chosen hues and switched the icon from the NiceAdmin one to a custom made wissen-vernetzen logo. Then, I adapted the dashboard to the requirements for the charts and also added another page for the ontology description. The main components that I used were cards for content display, a collapsible bar for the menu and the pre-set header and footer for further information. The footer is placed at the end of the page and visible when users scroll all the way down; the header, however, is sticky and always visible.

On the main page, I added a card for the information text, then two cards for the diagrams underneath. Instead of placing the information text on the side, as I had intended in the original design, I decided to centralise it, as the menu (when not collapsed) would significantly minimise or overlap it. I also included the headings for the maps according to their content and functionality. For the interactive charts, I added a button that would take the user directly to the KG search input field. Users can zoom in, zoom out and move around in these charts. Hovering over a bubble in the

⁴⁵For the website development procedures, I used WebStorm 2023.2 as IDE.

Network Visualisation with Hairball Effect.

Decluttered Visualisation without Hairball Effect.

Figure 45: Hairball Effect: Tightly connected datasets with many, interconnected nodes become less informative with an increasing number of nodes on the chart, which clutter the entire visualisation. Visualisation taken from Lanum (2014).

addressee visualisation shows the frequency of correspondence with Constance de Salm. All diagram cards have short instructions for the user on how to use them.

Subsequently, I appended another card that would contain the KG visualisation. I inserted a heading, subheading and an instruction (101) for using the graph interface. The instructions include hints for loading, interacting with and searching in the graph. An embedded window contains the KG visualisation. I then further adapted this visualisation: I changed the colours and icons of the individual nodes depending on their class and added a picture of Constance to Salm to her node. I also set which information should appear in the infoboxes when users click on the nodes. I adjusted the default settings for interacting with the network to prevent double assignments or disturbing effects. Clicking on a node displays the infobox, right-clicking opens the link in a new tab. Originally, only hovering caused the infobox to appear; however, some infoboxes overlap a part of the graph, making many nodes in the periphery invisible or difficult to hover.

While testing this first version, I already noticed that the graph visualisation takes an extremely long time to load. In order to communicate what is happening on the page, I attached a loading indicator (spinner) to the graph card that is visible as long as the graph data is loading. Other content on the website is unaffected. Unfortunately, the visualisation of the entire graph with all entries takes so long to load that windows from standard browsers like Opera or Chrome freeze and crash. Whenever the window did not crash, the visualisation was hardly decipherable and did not provide much information (see Figure 45 for comparison of what a hairball-ish network visualisation looks like). I opted for a reduced version of the graph for the visualisation instead; this

```
1 <script>
2   function loadGraphInitial(jsonFile) {
3     document.onreadystatechange = function () {
4       init(jsonFile);
5       if (document.readyState !== "complete") {
6         document.getElementById("neo4jd3").style.visibility = "hidden";
7         document.getElementById("loading_indicator").style.visibility =
8           "visible";
9       } else {
10        setTimeout(() => {
11          document.getElementById("loading_indicator").style.display =
12            "none";
13          document.getElementById("neo4jd3").style.visibility = "visible";
14        }, 9000)
15      }
16    };
17  }
18 </script>
```

Listing 2: JavaScript Code for Loading Indicator.

visualisation has a short loading time (only a few seconds if users have a stable and fast internet connection) but does not let the browser crash. The version encompasses a sub-graph of all transcribed texts and their contextual information.

Next, I implemented the search in the KG in JavaScript. The function I implemented for this is relatively simple and based on word matching between a user's input and the data in the graph. At its core, this function compares an input string (line 37–40 in the code snippet shows the parsing of it) to entries in the entire graph (line 17–23) based on a regular expression and then grabs subgraphs that contain the string in designated properties. These properties are a letter's year, addressee, sender, keyword, or sentiment. A letter can also be filtered according to its template status (original, copy). Then, the function collects all results in a match list (see line 14–33 in the code snippet) and initiates a new graph with the updated, filtered output.

Thereupon I re-adjusted some interaction functionalities in the graph when the filtered version is displayed in accordance with Figure 41: Double-clicking a node expands its contextual environment. This means that more nodes besides the result subgraph are displayed and overwrite the previously shown result (as Figure 46 visualises). Generally, this interaction is bound to the filtered graph version and double-clicking a node in the full graph (init state) has no effect.

As final part of the KG visualisation, I added a button for reloading the graph to its initial comprehensive state.

The next steps were to add the other pages I have already listed in Figure 42 and to adjust the navigation menu. First, I added the files for these new pages to the

```
1 <script>
2   // GRAB USER INPUT
3   const search = document.getElementById('search');
4   // MATCHLIST WILL CONTAIN MATCHES FROM THE GRAPH
5   const matchList = document.getElementById('matchList');
6   let jsondata;
7
8   // GET CONTEXTUAL DATA FROM GRAPH JSON
9   const getJsonData = async () => {
10    const res = await fetch('json/cds-wv_fv-special.json');
11    jsondata = await res.json();
12  };
13
14  const searchInput = async searchText => {
15    //console.log(jsondata['results'][0]['data']);
16    // GET MATCHES TO CURRENT INPUT
17    let matches = jsondata['results'][0]['data'].filter(datapoint => {
18      const regex = new RegExp(`^${searchText}`, 'gi');
19      if (
20        datapoint.graph.nodes[0]['properties']['wv__has_year'] != undefined
21        &&
22        datapoint.graph.nodes[0]['properties']['wv__has_year'] == searchText
23        ||
24        // AND SO ON...
25      ) {
26        return (datapoint)
27      }
28    });
29    data.results[0].data = matches;
30    // INIT GRAPH WITH NEW, FILTERED RESULTS
31    initModdedGraph(data, jsondata, rawJson);
32  };
33
34  window.addEventListener('DOMContentLoaded', getJsonData);
35  function returnText() {
36    let input = document.getElementById("userInput").value;
37    searchInput(input);
38  }
39 </script>
```

Listing 3: JavaScript Code for Keyword Search (Simplified).

Figure 46: Double-Click on Nodes: a double-click on a node in a filtered subgraph expands to show its context.

Figure 47: Adapted Template: KG visualisation.

project repository (the Contact and FAQ pages were already there in the template) and adjusted the links to these pages in the menu bar. For the FAQ page I added two tabs, one for the basic questions (and answers) and another for a short ontology overview. The question card is divided into six different questions, all annotated with subheadings and a body with textual output. From the ontology overview the user can jump to the full definition via links. The ontology tab describes all the classes I have defined with short texts and examples from the graph. At the bottom of this page is a download card where users can download the relevant files from the project by clicking on the link. On the contact page, I listed information about my social media contacts, the GitHub repositories, and my current email address for questions. In order to find out how real users would react to this website, I had a group of researchers and interns from DHIP test it during a workshop I held.

5.3 Usability Testing

In this last step of the implementation, I dealt with testing and review to make sure that everything works as intended in different browsers and devices. To do this, I checked that all content was displayed as intended and met my design requirements. Afterwards, I held a workshop on digital history at the DHIP, where I presented this Master's thesis project as an example. As a task for those present, I asked them to open the website and explore it without much guidance. The phase should allow improvements and refinements to the website. Users' feedback helped me to iterate upon the design and improve the website. The slides are included in the appendix (Figure 53–Figure 62).

Usability testing is used to evaluate a product or service and determine the overall UX. Typically, such a test involves representative users trying to perform typical tasks while being observed. Observing potential future users helps to unveil problems with the interface and overall product (e.g. a website). Moreover, collecting qualitative and quantitative data can help to determine how satisfied a user is with the application. A usability test can be followed by a survey of the participants (e.g. SUS, System Usability Scale, which quantifies satisfaction with the system) (Shneiderman et al., 2006, pp. 188–197; Lewis, 2012).

According to Shneiderman et al. (2006), the basis for a good usability test is given when representative participants interact with representative scenarios. Therefore I invited researchers of different scientific background to the workshop. In total, I invited a number of seven people. Two hold a PhD in (art) history and are permanent employees at the DHIP. One participant was of non-scientific background and normally works in administration. The rest of the group consisted of students of different ages and stages of study who were doing an internship at the time. Their fields of study include history,

Questions:

- Why is the website in English?
- Is it possible to transfer the names directly to the graph from the overviews and search that way?
- Will there be a translation?
- Are these all letters?

Notes:

- On mobile devices, the graph is not perfectly manageable; nodes cannot be addressed by right-clicking and generally interaction via touch (except zooming) is poor.
- On mobile devices, the menu overlaps the logo, clicking on it and opening it is impossible (accidentally clicking the logo reloads the homepage).
- There is no error message when you search for a word for which no results are found in the graph. Then, only a blank window is displayed and users were confused whether something is still loading or if something crashed. In general, it is unclear which words can be searched for and which cannot.
- The instructions are too long and it takes too long to get to the knowledge graph visualisation. Users suggested to move the extensive instructions to the F.A.Q. and to move the short ontology description to the homepage instead. It was wished to include small tooltips with hints instead.
- The testers found that the bugs on the site were sometimes very confusing, as they were annoying and not expected: The site supposedly looks so professional that they assumed everything would work perfectly.

Figure 48: Questions and Remarks During Think-Aloud Phase: The participants' notes on their experience with the website.

cultural and library/information sciences. Most of the participants had previously worked with web interfaces of DSEs, but had little or no experience with semantic technologies or the functionality of LOD.

After a short introduction of what digital history is and an introduction of other general terms like artificial intelligence, research data management or Semantic Web, I let the group freely discover the website on their devices. Some used laptops to do so, others opened it on their mobile phones.⁴⁶ I asked participants to comment on what they were doing during the exploration (think-aloud approach) and also to provide global feedback after they had finished.

They had fifteen minutes to roam the website's contents. During the execution, when participants voiced concerns or doubts or when I had the feeling that they did not know what else to do, I gave subtle hints for tasks, such as searching for a keyword in the graph or opening a node's URL in a new tab. During the think-aloud phase, I recorded all the questions and comments of the participants in a notebook. I then, after the fifteen minutes test phase, asked the participants questions about overall usability, other problems and wishes for the website. Additionally, I asked them if they understood the general purpose and tasks on the website and if they would use it again. In order not to exhaust the group, I refrained from using a SUS to quantify the results.

The results from Figure 48 show that there were some more serious misunderstandings and ambiguities on the website in its first version. These include, in particular, the lack

⁴⁶I did not specifically adapt the website to mobile use but the Bootstrap template already included refinements for display on smartphones or the like.

Figure 49: Improvements of the Website: users receive a warning when a search query was not found in the KG.

of error messages or calls to action when something did not work. As this error was noted by several people from the test group, it was particularly frequent and had a negative impact on usability, as it shows a major lack of communication between the application and the users. In general, the feedback was positive and there were not many questions about the benefits and functionality of the website. The interaction with the KG visualisation worked intuitively for most of the group and interactions like zooming, clicking for information, etc. were figured out by the people themselves (together with the textual instructions). The design and the fact that the site runs smoothly without any problems were appreciated. Furthermore, the fact that a loading indicator appears when charging the graph visualisation was also positively highlighted.

Based on the feedback, I iterated on the website and adjusted things that were negatively commented on. For example, I added a pop-up window that indicates when a search has failed, which I illustrate in Figure 49. I also adjusted some of the text and shortened some of the headings. Due to time constraints and the difficulty of making major changes in the behaviour and appearance of the KG visualisation, I was not able to implement all the notes. This includes, for example, shortening the user guide and adding some tooltips in the visualisation itself. Nevertheless, this is planned for future work, as well as other adjustments that I discuss in section 6.

6 Discussion

This chapter recapitulates the research question of how LOD approaches and KGs help to improve the reusability and (visual) presentation of research data from smaller digitisation projects; I evaluate key findings in terms of renewed accessibility to research data and the general application of LOD to historical data. I tie the results to existing research on semantic technologies in DSEs in general and letter correspondences in particular, and pinpoint the limitations I encountered during the project.

This discussion stresses the transdisciplinary potential of standardised LOD approaches for historical data. I also show how an exploratory KG visualisation and enriched, contextualised information promote the accessibility and reusability of research data from smaller digitisation projects, while opening up new horizons for interdisciplinary engagement. This includes validating that the KG, despite its prototypical nature, works as a proof of concept for the research question.

The major results of the project include the successful transformation of the Constance de Salm data basis into a standardised LOD approach, the development of a comprehensive KG, the transcription of a subset of letters and the integration of text mining results into the graph, as well as the implementation of a user-friendly website. Using ideas from the Semantic Web, ontologies and KGs, I converted the previously proprietary data to open formats (CSV, RDF/XML), earning the database two more LOD stars in accordance with Berners-Lee's model. The KG is still under construction and is currently a prototype. The same applies to the website, which is a beta version.

To do all this, I developed a reusable, semi-automatic pipeline to help process the data through the KG creation, text mining and semantic enrichment stages. I also created a baseline ontology from which I later built the KG, which now contains all the original metadata from the correspondence, as well as contextual information and text mining results from this project.

So far, I have managed to standardise most of the metadata in the Constance de Salm corpus of letters. The standardisation covers both data formats and metadata content such as names of correspondents, places of exhibition, keywords and sentiments. Due to the graph representation, letters no longer exist singularly (as entries in rows), they are interconnected entities in a web of information. The NLP results are also directly available within this graph.

Although I did not develop a suitable ATR model for the original letters of Constance de Salm, I did transcribe a subset of nine letters, which users can query using keyword searches.

In parallel with the data transformation, I implemented a user-friendly website to present the project results. The beta version contains a searchable, interactive KG

visualisation, ontology definitions and introductory correspondence material.

Overall, the successful implementation of a standardised LOD approach and KG for Constance de Salm's correspondence has significant implications for both digital humanities research and RDM in general. The standardisation of research data goes hand in hand with the application of the FAIR principles and thus improves overall findability, reusability, accessibility, etc. Especially for small and medium sized research institutions, following such standards in research data management helps with long-term preservation and versioning of data. This tackles the challenge of data fragmentation and the risk of data becoming obsolete by adhering to open standards and structured data formats. Following these motifs, this Master's thesis project demonstrates a commitment to best practice and ensures the longevity and availability of historical data. It aims to bridge the gap between the humanities and technology by demonstrating the power of Semantic Web principles in preserving and presenting the past for present and future generations.

In addition to ensuring the accessibility and reusability of historical data, this project sets an example for possible presentation of research results. Furthermore, by integrating NLP results into the KG, it introduces a new contextual layer that enhances historical searching within the correspondence and provides a comprehensive view of connections within the data. In this way, the KG acts as a portal to deeper insights brought about by exploratory search, potentially unlocking hidden patterns and correlations.

The transformation pipeline and, finally, the visualisation on the website show the many different possibilities that LOD approaches bring to research data. These include not only accessibility or long-term preservation, but also integration into a larger research context. Despite its prototypical nature, the application of my pipeline shows that it is possible to standardise and LOD-ify a collection of metadata in a one-person project, and thus provides a perspective for other research groups to follow suit. Even a small corpus was enough to visualise the data on the website, implement the transformation pipeline and lay the groundwork for further updates. This result underlines the strength of smart, small data.

The interplay between provided information in the interactive KG visualisation and the website enables a synergistic platform that revitalises access to the correspondence. Being available as a downloadable file, users can obtain, view and modify the graph as they wish on their local machine, but the focus is on the visualisation that provides access to interact with the graph. Initially I did not expect the website and visualisation part of this project to be so difficult and thought it would be easier to find a good framework for my requirements. I suggest that the problems stem from my lack of

proficiency in web development, a decent front-end developer might have had better luck implementing things exactly as desired.

The findings are in line with existing research from the same domain, particularly in digital history and humanities. As Wettlaufer (2018) notes, interest in linking DSEs using LOD and Semantic Web approaches is growing rapidly, but feasibility and relevance have yet to be proven in real-world applications. This project brings these approaches together and tries to put into practice what has been mostly theoretical so far. Digital historians, researchers who create DSEs and other people from academia have and continue to recognise the perspectives offered by graph technologies and the Semantic Web to facilitate interdisciplinary data sharing, interoperability and content representation. These perspectives concern, for example, the need to structure research data obtained from historical sources in appropriate formalised models that can be used alongside algorithms such as text mining to collect and contextualise information in a historical ontology or vocabulary (Meroño-Peñuela et al., 2015). KGs help with simpler and clearer storage of (formerly) unstructured data (Dörpinghaus, 2022). Accordingly, this thesis combines computational methods and traditional historical research, as well as the integration of text mining results into KGs, demonstrating the potential of NLP in digital history to transform raw historical data into structured knowledge (Meroño-Peñuela et al., 2015).

As with other similar projects, this thesis is exploratory in spirit, as there is little to no guideline on the use of semantic technologies in humanities research. Isolated solutions help projects in an encapsulated way, not providing guidance for other future research in the same area (Wettlaufer, 2018, p. 12); this project tries to overcome this hurdle by providing an exemplary how-to-do-it with recyclable pipelines for ontology creation, KG implementation and semantic enrichment via text mining. I created an ontology to describe the content of the corpus of letters, which can be used by other projects wishing to describe their correspondence using a Semantic Web approach. This underscores the potential for broader collaboration and data sharing within the Semantic Web framework. Existing ontology definitions and vocabularies such as FOAF and SKOS facilitate data integration, interoperability, comparability, automation and data sharing in further open science approaches. However, the consequence of this is that although a connection is drawn to more general vocabularies that describe the classes and relationships in the ontology, it cuts out the addressability of a set of entities that are not yet present in standard reference systems such as GND or GeoNames. Due such fuzziness in the data, I had to consider modelling approaches that address missing URLs and the like and note it accordingly on the website. Unfortunately, this was not possible for all persons or keywords without a reference and is a future task of

the project (Dumont, 2019, pp. 15–16). Wetzlauber’s (2018) question of whether all knowledge in humanities research can be represented in a single ontology is consequently also denied in this project because I used different vocabularies and combined concepts to describe the metadata in the correspondence. This suggests that an omnipotent ontology is dystopian in even larger applications than Constance de Salm’s corpus of letters, in which I did not extensively describe all concepts. Nevertheless, I share his future ideas of connecting all projects through a LOD hub like Wikidata, for which I have already added links to entities in the Constance de Salm KG (Wetzlauber, 2018, 12–14).

Another frequently mentioned issue is change-aware modelling, which helps to keep track of changes in entities over time. Such change-aware modelling is still relatively new to ontologies, but applies to a wide range of subjects, such as geographical names, name spelling or known dates of events. I have tried to incorporate this by linking the correspondence data to external repositories and including alternative labels defined there. Automatic updates are not yet possible, but this would be an add-on for future optimisations of the model and the website (Meroño-Peñuela et al., 2015; Wetzlauber, 2018). Furthermore, such statements could be modelled using RDF*, which extends RDF with the possibility to make statements about statements (Arndt et al., 2023).

Dörpinghaus (2022) points out that contextual information is a crucial factor in data-driven evaluations and that, however, such holistic perspectives on research were rare. A lack of linked data and methods for large-scale KGs therefore poses a limitation. The project presented in this thesis tackles this point by integrating the correspondence of Constance de Salm in a standardised ontology and following the Semantic Web principles. This enhances the value of possible historical research with (contextualised) data from the corpus of letters. The special nature of data heterogeneity and the associated technical challenges in the area of data integration and data mapping and thus the generation of interoperable and reusable data are also dealt with in this Master’s thesis. The use of standardised ontologies and controlled vocabularies resonates with efforts to establish common metadata models for enhanced data sharing and accessibility for content that is not project-specific. Former standardisation and structuring of the data helped to improve integration and avoid errors when adding new, external information to the graph (e.g. from Wikidata or GND). By enriching the semantic annotation with text mining results, I added another layer of contextualisation to the letter’s metadata.

Dörpinghaus (2022) also remarks that LOD principles and KGs in the (digital) humanities combine network analysis approaches with new perspectives, as they embed the known in a new visual or analytical context. Besides visual networks like in sociology, semantics visualisation allows for renewed, intuitive access to the connections

and patterns in data bases, revealing a further level of accessibility and knowledge, which is particularly evident in letter correspondences (high level of interdependence between documents, topics, etc.) (Baillot, 2018). The underlying structures in KGs allow information to be found more easily and, although research in this area mainly focuses on machine-readability of data, human-centred systems, especially visualisations, can also benefit. As DSEs have increasingly turned to digital platforms to present a conglomerate of types of information, developing interactive and user-friendly interfaces has emerged as a crucial endeavour, which also influenced this project in aiming to develop a like-wise user-friendly website and interactive KG visualisation as entry point to the Constance de Salm correspondence. It should support engagement, intuitive exploration, and human interaction with semantics. Visualisations offer graphical guidance for understanding the structure of data; entities (resources), relationships and all their contextualised information (Nazemi, 2016; Nazemi et al., 2015). Nazemi (2016) found that full-adaptive semantics visualisations work efficiently and effectively for reducing cognitive load and effort, thereby increasing satisfaction and user experience in human-semantics interaction. Principles like interactivity, adaption and usability find resonance in this thesis' focus on making historical research data accessible to a wider audience. With a reduced version of the KG, I intended to reduce cognitive load on non-experienced users (Cambridge Intelligence, 2022; Lanum, 2014; Venturini et al., 2021). The resulting website and KG visualisation serve as portals to engage novices and interdisciplinary researchers to navigate the correspondence and extract insights that transcend disciplinary boundaries through dynamic, adaptive exploration. This aligns with the broader discourse on usability in digital humanities, where efforts are directed towards creating interfaces that facilitate meaningful interactions with complex data sets (Bleier & Klug, 2018; Dumont, 2018; Novak et al., 2014).

Overall, the possibilities to contextualise knowledge, to formally describe content, to annotate digital documents with semantic technologies and the display of DSEs as interfaces on the web address a recurrent issue in digital (historical) research. Applying principles from the Semantic Web and KGs to research data resonates with the broader movement to establish open data, just like standardised vocabularies and models across various domains in the digital humanities, as proposed by consortia like NFDI4Memory or the like. Computational tools that intersect with historical research questions open up new avenues for understanding the past and, in doing so, reinforce potential research questions for historical data through sophisticated methodologies (Dörpinghaus, 2022; Fickers, 2022; Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI) e.V., 2023a; Zaagsma, 2013).

Although the results are largely in line with the research question and milestones,

they are not without limitations. The term ‘prototype’ indicates that this project is still in the development stage. Therefore, various aspects, starting with refining ontology definitions, improving the KG and text mining methods, and eventually implementing the website, require further optimisation. In particular, the ATR process is still underdeveloped. The lack of an ATR model for the original letters of Constance de Salm underlines the complexity of automating transcription tasks, especially for historical handwritten documents, as known from previous research studies (Biay, 2022).

Beyond that, refining the ontology definitions is crucial to improve the accuracy and effectiveness of the KG to describe other (currently missing) core elements of the Constance de Salm correspondence: updates to entities (correcting labels) and additional classes to describe personal relationships, or linking keywords and sentiments to other resources will allow for more reliable insights and analysis. The reliance on existing ontologies raises concerns about the accurate representation of the nuanced historical context and terminology in the correspondence, and points to the need for advanced ontology development that encompasses the unique challenges of historical research (Wettlaufer, 2018).

I also did not transcribe as many texts as I had originally intended. This problem is due to both the lack of a suitable ATR model and the limited time frame of this thesis. Nevertheless, I achieved my goal of creating a small smart corpus that I could integrate into the KG. In the future, the results could be used to validate and compare findings, detect patterns and trends in more detail for individual letters. This serves as a proof of concept that text mining can indeed serve as a distant reading tool to extract insights from historical documents such as letters for semantic enrichment and annotation.

Using existing NLP and text mining frameworks for Python, I have achieved reasonable results for the subset of letters. While this adds to the value of the database, it is important to acknowledge the problems, which mostly result from the relatively small subset of transcribed letters. Whilst this highlights that it is indeed possible to generate such a complex and comprehensive KG from a small dataset, it prevents a global understanding of concepts in the correspondence that go beyond the subset. Moreover, the Python frameworks that I used are not specialised for historical data and might distort results. This is especially the case for sentiment analysis, because the model stems from analysis of film reviews. A similar problem also concerns the key phrase extraction, which did not work optimally for the letters. Improving text mining methods in the future might enable more efficient and accurate extraction of relevant information and knowledge from a large corpus of letters. This information could further enrich the KG and allow for a broader exploration of the data basis by a larger variety of keywords and subject terms.

This problem also affects the final KG visualisation: not all letters are available within it. While a smaller visualisation of a KG can reduce cognitive load, it can influence users' perception negatively and seed confusion as to why, in a corpus of around 11,000 letters, only nine are searchable. The hereby identified problem is not directly solvable in this thesis but calls for action in future research. For now, the advantages of a smaller visualisation outweigh; besides a shorter loading time in the browser, the reduced size allows users to focus on individual elements and their connections without being overwhelmed by complexity (and irrelevant nodes and edges that crowd the screen). The visualisation is meant as a prototype that can be expanded upon with larger data sets in the future.

It was equally difficult to find an easy-to-use RDF visualisation tool. Since there is little choice in this area and I did not have much time or resources, I had to switch to Neo4j and Labeled Property Graphs. The entire venture is not entirely unproblematic, since although LPGs provide similar and partially better means for storing graph-like data, they do not fit into the basic principles of the Semantic Web. In future applications, it is definitely necessary to develop better tools for RDF visualisations and offer them as free, open source applications. Then it would also be possible to grant queries in interactive KGs not only by keywords or full text, but also by tools that support the translation of natural language queries to SPARQL (Bhajikhaye, 2021).

Last but not least, it should be discussed how the usability testing of the website can be improved. I had only a small group examine the website's and received mostly positive feedback and hints for immediate improvements; however, it would also be beneficial to apply quantifiable tests on usability and user experience with a bigger group of participants. Having a group of users accompany further adjustments and optimisations of the website with direct input for wishes and concerns would help to retrieve the best possible interface (for a similar study approach in usability testing for semantics visualisation, see Nazemi (2016)).

All of the developments presented serve as a basis for future research. I envisage extending the KG to include a larger dataset, i.e. a larger number of letters written not only by Constance de Salm but also by other people in the correspondence, which would allow the information in the KG to be more tightly linked, and would also allow letters to be linked to other historical correspondences. For example, Constance de Salm has several letters to and from Alexander von Humboldt. There is also a DSE of von Humboldt's letters which could then be linkable to this graph. This could provide a more complete understanding of the historical relationships, especially in relation to certain events and circumstances. Speaking of events, it would also be possible to semi-automatically extract events and other content information from the letters and

model this information in the graph. Such semantic enrichment through advanced text mining techniques, combined with an extended corpus of letter transcriptions, promises a deeper understanding of the history of Constance de Salm and her contemporaries.

Bedenkt man, wie umfangreich Gelehrtenkorrespondenzen etwa im 18. Jahrhundert sein konnten, wäre dies ein größeres Unterfangen, aber kein unmögliches. Und wenn jeder Forscher und jede Forscherin etwas Ähnliches über den jeweiligen Hausautor anlegen würden, hätte man letztlich die Möglichkeit, diese Ego-netzwerke entweder über Personen, über Werke, über Orte oder über Themen miteinander zu einem größeren Netzwerk zu verknüpfen. [Considering how extensive scholarly correspondences could be in the 18th century, for example, this would be a major undertaking, but not impossible. And if every researcher were to create something similar about the respective house author, one could eventually link these first-person networks about people, about works, about places or about topics into a larger network] (Baillot, 2018).

Add to that an optimised visual representation of the KG with more insightful, aesthetically presented infoboxes that could further enhance user engagement and insightfulness. Generally, the entire website could profit from exploration of other semantics visualisation techniques, new interactive features, and advanced explorative searches. The collaboration with other research projects or crowd-sourcing would offer shared ontology development – potentially surpassing the domain of Constance de Salm and motivating other, smaller digitisation undertakings to join in.

I would also like to emphasise the importance of future research in the area of standardised, LOD-ified, smart data and KG approaches for (digital) humanities, history and beyond. With an ever-growing reservoir of possibilities for generating, analysing and visualising data, the synergy between technology and research can become ever more deeply rooted. Making research data from all disciplines available in open, accessible formats can open up new possibilities for different audiences, which in turn can amplify knowledge discovery. RDM, the Semantic Web and semantic hubs, if applied properly and frequently, can foster the interdisciplinary and ubiquitous dialogue.

Through this project, I hope to contribute to the growth of a semantic hub for the humanities: even working with a *petit corpus* could lay the groundwork for future research. Users can dive directly into the correspondence of said *petit corpus* and interact with and explore the data within a single visualisation, encouraging hands-on discovery of relationships and concepts.

7 Conclusion

In this project, I aspired to emphasise the importance of 1) reusing data from smaller digitisation projects, 2) structuring data for better accessibility and 3) the insightfulness that can come from analysing a *petit corpus*. In the context of recent developments in RDM, digital humanities and DSEs, I aimed to investigate how LOD approaches and KGs improve reusability and (visual) presentation of research data from smaller digitisation projects, while also providing a proof of concept application. Hand in hand with this research focus, the project aimed to illustrate the potential of small data and how its analysis generates new knowledge; adding these results to the KG that has been developed should act as a gateway to the project's hidden data.

Throughout this thesis, the Constance de Salm correspondence served as example to illustrate the potential of LOD approaches and KGs for DH. In essence, the key findings, like the successful transformation of the entire database into open, non-proprietary formats and the development of a prototypical knowledge graph with enhanced, contextual information about the correspondence showcase how Semantic Web and LOD approaches support transdisciplinary work with data through standardised structures and formats. Integrating text mining results for semantic enrichment demonstrated the transformative potential of smaller corpora. The results emphasise the importance of adhering to open standards for research data, their management, publication and presentation, independent of a project's size. Contextualised information provided by principles of FAIR and linked open data helps to give the letters renewed accessibility and applicability. Furthermore, with the interactive knowledge graph visualisation and the user-friendly website, both of which provide exploratory access to the correspondence, I aimed to innovate the presentation of historical data derived from the correspondence. This also included evaluating how valuable this façon of exploration is for novices.

The inclusion of NLP results adds a layer of contextualisation, enriching the metadata and enabling more dynamic possibilities for search and exploration. Generally, the semantics visualisation and all additional information on the website facilitate research within the domain. They set an example for effective presentation of results, promoting usability and reusability, although provided with only a small set of data. The workflow and its results prototypically demonstrate the feasibility of LOD approaches for enhanced accessibility and (re-)usability of (historical) research data, also seeking to extend the reach of Constance de Salm and her extensive corpus of letters. Having an interactive, partially adaptive KG visualisation on the website is a pioneering effort to make research data more appealing to a wider audience, and provides an exemplary approach to how DSEs of correspondences could visualise the interconnectivity in their databases on

GUIs.

It is crucial to consider how ongoing developments around OA, OD and OS affect RDM and the global shift in how the research community values and manages data. This Master's thesis project presented the benefits of applying OS and OD, as well as LOD and FAIR principles, to processing, analysing and sharing research data. Interdisciplinary research methods such as sentiment analysis or standardised ontology building helped to ensure data quality and to extract new knowledge that enriches the correspondence data.

While the project successfully demonstrated the transformative impact of LOD and KG approaches, challenges in terms of usability and user comprehension, especially in terms of explorative, semantic visualisation, have impacted the final results. The results portray potential milestones for the field, but do not go without limitations. In particular, those concern the prototypical nature of the KG and the website. Moreover, especially the ATR for Constance de Salm's handwriting stays a mammoth task. These limitations, however, do not diminish the findings' contributions and the possibility for expansion and refinement for other projects with similar endeavours.

In terms of the broad domain that are DH, the results are in line with emerging trends in the integration of semantic technologies into interdisciplinary humanities research. They demonstrate a practical implementation of Semantic Web and FAIR principles, bridging the gap between technology and traditional research. They advocate for openness, accessibility and reusability of data. In accordance with findings from similar undertakings, this project demonstrates the power of standardised data models and ontologies to make historical, heterogeneous research data more structured and interconnected, and promotes the creation of semantic hubs for the domain. Ideas on change-aware modelling, as well as semantic enrichment through keyword extraction and sentiment analysis address recurring needs of DH projects and the dynamic character of digital data sets like the correspondence of Constance de Salm.

The "Open Humanities, Open Culture" motto promises to reshape practices for research data in current and future projects in the humanities. Next to big organisations or initiatives like the EOSC, NFDI, or in general FAIR principles, such changes also influence small- and medium-sized research institutions. While guidelines offer roadmaps for the future, the actual application in real-world scenarios stays a challenge. This thesis contributes to the ongoing question concerning the 'how' by redefining the boundaries of historical research in terms of visual representation and FAIRness. Working with the correspondence of Constance de Salm has demonstrated a profound potential of Semantic Web principles and ontologies within the domain of DSEs and similar.

Since the field of DH is constantly evolving and graph technologies are also subject to

constant change, as well as levelled by the fact that the results presented are prototypes, the scope for follow-up research is quite vast. Results from this project could be used for further expansion of databases, serve as baselines for ontology creation, or novel ways of thinking about DSEs' interfaces. Future perspectives for this project include, for example on a technological level, improvements concerning the entire website and the KG visualisation. It would be feasible to switch to a more modern JS library like React.js or Vue.js for more possibilities concerning interface design, embedding in WordPress or the creation of flexible interface components. Correspondingly, there are many opportunities to ameliorate the KG in terms of presentation of contextual information in infoboxes, the compartment of nodes, or the like. Additionally, another engaging and innovative method for upgrading the visualisation would be integrating a virtual and/or augmented reality component, i.e. a three-dimensional network that users could explore and interact with.

At the centre of possible improvements is, above all, an increase in the size of the data basis – utilising not only Constance de Salm's letters and, most importantly, a larger quantity of transcribed documents –, which presupposes that a suitable ATR model would have to be trained. In addition to the challenge of developing such a model for the complicated manuscripts, finding suitable text mining models for French historical texts would be another hurdle. In the case of de Salm's correspondence, it might be worthwhile to train a sentiment analysis or emotion detection model or something similar from scratch, based on the results of manual analyses of the emotions or sentiments of the letters. With adjustments to the existing ontology, new text mining results would join the repertoire of contextual information about the correspondence.

Other, more traditional research questions would open up and become easier to answer based on such an additional result. In the scope of a dissertation project, further semantic annotation and text mining methods could help to pursue the research question of how Constance de Salm's writing changed over the years and with changing locations (Paris/France, Castle Dyck/Rhineland/Germany). Last but not least, the use of semantic technologies and LOD-ified data could be strengthened by creating links between the metadata, the transcribed texts and the digital copies themselves. Upgrading the underlying data model from RDF to RDF* is also an approachable future perspective for describing historical circumstances.

With this work I aspire to contribute to the expanding field of LOD in the (digital) humanities. I intend to provide the data in such a way that they are easily reusable and interoperable, thus adhering to the FAIR principles. This project thus encourages thinking about LOD as natural part of the handling and management of data in FAIR research and highlights the potential of KGs to connect multiple sources in a semantic

hub to provide a more holistic view of research data. At the same time, this project supports the principles of open science and open data: this stance aims to transcend disciplinary boundaries, promoting a good scientific practice that allows even small corpora to unfold their potential and in which LOD are intrinsic.

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A Appendix

Figure 50: Website Mockup Idea Without Charts: One of the first mockups for the website, without charts and only the knowledge graph visible.

Figure 51: Website Mockup Idea With Charts: Charts after knowledge graph visualisation.

Figure 52: Website Mockup Idea With Menu: Menu design idea for different pages of the website.

Figure 53: Workshop Slide 1: Title slide.

Figure 54: Workshop Slide 2: Plan of the workshop.

Figure 55: Workshop Slide 3: Overview of definitions.

Figure 56: Workshop Slide 4: Overview of definitions.

Figure 57: Workshop Slide 5: Overview of definitions.

Figure 58: Workshop Slide 6: Overview of definitions.

Figure 59: Workshop Slide 7: Overview of different aspects of the project.

Figure 60: Workshop Slide 8: Introduction of user interfaces for historical data.

Figure 61: Workshop Slide 9: Introduction to usability testing and central points of the website.

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LUST AUF MEHR?

Blog:
Programmieren ist
(k)ein Hexenwerk

Blog:
Data, Data, there to
Crawl, Who's the Fairest
of Them All?

Poster (Peter-Haber-
Preis)

Figure 62: Workshop Slide 10: Codes and question round.